

THE PILGRIM'S PROGRESS: A RELATABLE AND TIMELESS JOURNEY FOR THE
CHURCH OF CHRIST

by

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Abstract

John Bunyan's *The Pilgrim's Progress* has left a remarkable reputation after its 1678 and 1684 release. The book sold over 100,000 copies in its first decade of print¹ and translated in 200 languages since publication.² With its critical reception, what value is the book's message for the latter-day? Why did Bunyan expound biblical truths in allegorical writing? Its pertinence pivots in Bunyan's pastoral mind frame, his audience, and biblical expositions, particularly with the doctrine of salvation and the Christian church. Prominent themes in Puritan teaching following Reformed doctrine are the atonement of Christ and its application. The textual evidence demonstrates an interrelation with the doctrine of salvation, and the redemptive identity of the church of Christ. Contemporary implications with J. Gresham Machen's publications *Christianity and Liberalism* are considered regarding biblical reform. Drawing from Puritan declarations and pastoral heart, I argue Bunyan's audience is the church of Christ. In writing to her, Bunyan's allegory constructs a doctrinal basis for the church and the stages of her Christian journey.

¹ Joel Beeke, and Randall J. Peterson, *Meet the Puritans: With a Guide to Modern Reprints*, (Reformation Heritage, 2006), 107.

² Beeke and Peterson, *Meet the Puritans*, Pg. 107.

Introduction

Contemporary questions regarding the identity and anchor of the church of Christ³ is a question of discussion for centuries. With recent movements of scholars attempting to redefine the church⁴ of Christ⁵ through a liberalist⁶ perspective, it comes to the question of the foundation of the church. When understanding the doctrinal⁷ view of the church of Christ poses questions about her identity:

For clarity, the church of Christ refers to the evangelical⁸ and protestant⁹ view of the church of Christ as "catholic,"¹⁰ The word "catholic" does not refer to the Roman Catholic Church.

³ Christ in the paper refers to “Jesus of Nazareth from the New Testament, and for the church, He is ‘fully divine and fully human, and await his promised second coming’” See Tim Dowley, *Introduction to the History of Christianity*, (Fortress Press Minneapolis., 3rd ed. 2018), 649.

⁴ James Bannerman’s book “The Church of Christ” provides definitions to the word ‘church’ according to its presentation in the Scriptures. For the paper’s focus on narrowing to the Reformer’s and its heirs (the Puritans), the following definitions are applicable to the word church referenced throughout this paper: “The word church signifies the whole body of the faithful, whether in heaven or on earth, who have been or shall be spiritually united to Christ as their savior” 1. James Bannerman, *The Church of Christ: A Treatise on the Nature, Powers, Ordinances, Discipline, and Government of the Christian Church*, (Carlisle, Pa: Banner of Truth Trust, 1974), 7.

“The term church is frequently employed in Scripture to denote the body of believers in any particular place, associated together in the worship of God.” Bannerman, *The Church of Christ*, 11.

“In the first place, the church is a divine institution, owing its origin not to man, but to Christ, and associated together not in consequences of human arrangement, but by Christ’s appointment.”

Bannerman, *The Church of Christ*, 19.

⁵ The words “Christ” and “God” are capitalized out of reverence and exaltation.

⁶ Protestant Liberalism teaches optionalism and it's the belief that God is able to forgive our sin apart from any specific Saviour acting on our behalf to satisfy God’s righteous demand. See Stephen Wellum, *Christ Alone: The Uniqueness of Jesus as Savior*, (Harper Collins & Zondervan. 2017), 33.

⁷ Doctrine can be defined as “a religious teaching or belief which is taught and upheld within a particular religious community” See Tim Dowley, *Introduction to the History of Christianity*, (Fortress Press Minneapolis., 3rd ed. 2018), 647. In addition, the scope of the paper and the doctrinal teaching of the church of Christ is according to the Reformers, particularly the Puritans who also adhered to tenets of the Reformation. Doctrinal implications from contemporary thought are also expounded.

⁸ Evangelical in the paper is defined as the emphasis of “the centrality of the Bible, justification by faith, and the need for personal conversion” See Dowley, *Introduction to the History of Christianity*, 647.

⁹ Protestantism in the paper will be defined as the following definition: “Christian faith and order as based on the principles of the Reformation. It emphasizes the sole authority of the Bible, justification by faith, and the priesthood of all believers. See Dowley, 653. Additionally, Dowley defined protestantism as “embracing liberal trends which have stressed the subjective side of religion since the nineteenth century.” See Dowley, 653. The latter definition is argued by J Gresham Machen in his book *Christianity and Liberalism*, which is used as a contemporary implication in the paper pertaining biblical reform as the basis for christianity and the church of Christ.

¹⁰ “Catholic” is defined as “possessing a high unity in the faith or profession of one Lord and Saviour,” Bannerman, *The Church of Christ*, 62.

With that said, the importance of doctrine helps solve the matter upon which the church is laid. Numerous men and women from the last two thousand years have committed their lives to defending the faith. In my paper, I will highlight a group of believers who have stood in the faith despite societal opposition. The same group of people have left their mark in history, and their literature continues to encourage and motivate Christians in future generations after their enoch. The Puritans were a group of Reformed Protestants during the 16th to 17th ¹¹ century who sought biblical reform in their personal lives, the lives of others, and the church of England. Puritan doctrine and experience will be highlighted to answer the three subsidiary questions from above. In addition, the life of author John Bunyan will be examined. Bunyan's life is worth exploring, mainly because of his testimony to Christianity. From being a blasphemer, understanding the weight of his sin¹² before God,¹³ experiencing heads on the goodness of the cross of Christ, preaching with a love for souls, assembling, and being jailed for preaching the gospel, Bunyan knew firsthand the Christian journey, and he wrote about it elaborately in his allegory *The Pilgrim's Progress*.

Bunyan's allegory continues to encourage and impact Christians in the twenty-first century. Upon examining his life and Puritan doctrine, the church's identity and salvation are woven into his writing and the focus of Puritan preaching. *The Pilgrim's Progress* is a small Puritan literature piece that has a repertoire of three hundred or so years of being a guide to Christ for sinners, the same lessons in every age. With such profound literature from a small

¹¹ For the scope of the paper, seventeenth-century Puritanism is the focus since Puritanism was a movement that had its spark for two centuries. For the scope of the paper, seventeenth-century Puritanism is highlighted and emphasized since Puritanism was a movement that had its spark for two centuries. Covering the two centuries of Puritanism being at its peak would be an ambitious task, and it would lose track of the paper and its focus. Additionally, the author of *The Pilgrim's Progress* Bunyan lived during the seventeenth century, published *The Pilgrim's Progress* in the seventeenth century, and several critical points in the religious battle between the Church of England and the Puritans Bunyan experienced hands-on effects, including but not limited to the act of uniformity. That said, not only is seventeenth-century Puritanism the scope, but also the seventeenth-century Puritan movement where Bunyan was alive, experienced its effects, and the circumstances from which *The Pilgrim's Progress* was published. Not only is seventeenth-century Puritanism the focus, but also the seventeenth-century Puritan movement when Bunyan was alive, who experienced its effects with the 1660 of the Restoration of the Monarchy.

¹² As the Puritans taught, sin was rebellion against the law and will of God, and it is both a corruption of human nature resulting from the fall of Adam and an action of individual disobedience. See Galen K. Johnson, and Charles Pastoor, *Historical Dictionary of the Puritans*, (Lanham, Md: Scarecrow Press. 2007), 300.

¹³ God is the "creator and sustainer of the universe; the absolute being on whom all that is depends. See Dowley, *Introduction to the History of Christianity*, 648.

group, what can people learn about the church of Christ in its readings? With *The Pilgrim's Progress*, readers will find a lot to take out of Bunyan's well-crafted allegory, for all the characters, objects, and locations have a significance grounded in old truths from the apostolic age and beforehand. Drawing from Puritan declarations and Bunyan's pastoral heart, I argue his audience is the church of Christ. In writing to her, Bunyan's allegory constructs a doctrinal basis for the church of Christ and the stages of her Christian journey. The following questions are examined through the background and textual evidence:

1. Why did Bunyan expound biblical truths of the Christian journey in allegorical writing?
2. What are the doctrinal implications of Bunyan's message to the audience, the church of Christ?

Background

1. The Puritans

Regarding the church's identity, it is essential to step back and evaluate a group of people with a collective goal to answer the exact question. They were devoted people who were doctrinally shaped, loved the Word of God, valued biblical preaching, wanted to be God-centered in their thoughts and lives, lived upright lives, and were not ashamed of their roots in the Reformation.¹⁴ The Puritans were English Protestants who sought thorough liturgical reform in the Church of England and individual lives from the sixteenth to the seventeenth century. The Puritans were also committed to identifying the distinctions between the church of Christ and their religious opponents and to nurturing the church of Christ through private, family, and corporate disciplines.¹⁵

The Puritans were not only a small but determined group of people with a significant impact on history,¹⁶ but they were also misunderstood and often stereotyped unjustly. The word "Puritan" was a derogatory term that referenced them amidst the religious competition, particularly of the "Papist" vs. the "Puritan."¹⁷ However, the key to understanding and getting the most out of the Puritans is recognizing their passionate love for the Bible as the written word of

¹⁴ David F. Wells, *The Courage to Be Protestant: Reformation Faith in Today's World*, Second ed, (Grand Rapids Michigan: William B. Eerdmans Publishing Company. 2017), 6.

¹⁵ Beeke and Reeves, *Following God Fully*, 79.

¹⁶ Johnson and Pastoor, *Historical Dictionary of the Puritans*, preface ix.

¹⁷ Beeke and Reeves, *Following God Fully*, 3.

God.¹⁸ In the spirit of the Reformers Martin Luther¹⁹ and John Calvin,²⁰ the Puritans sought complete inward and outward biblical results. They were discontent with the "almost" or "partially" biblical, for the Puritans believed an explicit instruction on church order was revealed in Scripture.²¹ The Puritans also devoted themselves to faithful preaching of Biblical principles and its application as true biblical counselors who understood that spiritual problems require spiritual solutions.²² It was not because they were a more "pure" group of people than their opponents; it was far from it. Instead, they reformed in an ongoing manner what in the church and themselves remained to be purified.²³ Regarding the church, the Puritans devoted their work to reforming the visible church,²⁴ her members,²⁵ and preserving her well-being through the conformity of the scriptures.²⁶

The Puritan's liturgical battle with the Church of England set an example of an enduring struggle for her²⁷ doctrinal identity. With Rome as their primary opponent, the monarchy implemented doctrinal views the Puritans believed were not the fairest and most accurate depiction of the church and biblical Christianity. For example, In a time when personal inspiration favored a consensual interpretation²⁸ of the Bible, preaching, literature, and catechisms²⁹ were the means the Puritans utilized to defend essential protestant doctrine.

¹⁸ Beeke and Reeves, *Following God Fully*, 4.

¹⁹ Martin Luther (1483-1546) was the founder of the German Reformation. He "held that people could be justified before God only by faith in Jesus Christ, not by any 'works' of religion. See Dowley, *Introduction to the History of Christianity*, 650.

²⁰ French theologian between 1509-64 that organized the Reformation from Geneva. He emphasized justification by faith and the sole authority of the Bible. See Dowley, *Introduction to the History of Christianity*, 645.

²¹ Beeke and Peterson, *Meet the Puritans*, preface xvii.

²² Don Kistler, *Why Read the Puritans Today?* (Northampton Press. 1999), 4

²³ Beeke and Reeves, *Following God Fully*, 3.

²⁴ In the study of Ecclesiology, there are two terms that are referenced: the invisible and visible church. The visible church is defined as believers who are "spiritually united to Christ, standing out visibly before the eyes of the world." Bannerman, *The Church of Christ*, 26. Additionally, the visible church is "known to men by the outward profession of faith in Him and by the practice of those church ordinances and observances which He has appointed for His worshippers." Bannerman, *The Church of Christ*, 26.

²⁵ Beeke and Reeves, *Following God Fully*, 3.

²⁶ Beeke and Reeves, *Following God Fully*, 3.

²⁷ In Scripture, the church has been referred to as the "holy bride of Christ, united to Him in an everlasting covenant - a society which He calls His spiritual Body, and of which He is the exalted head." Bannerman, *The Church of Christ*, 88.

²⁸ Johnson and Pastoor, *Historical Dictionary of the Puritans*, 290.

²⁹ A popular manual of Christian doctrine. See Dowley, *Introduction to the History of Christianity*, 645.

Additionally, several Puritan expressions have emerged in their liturgical battle, particularly the Separationists³⁰ and Nonconformists.³¹

With their zeal for biblical reform, the Puritans were no strangers to religious and political opposition. The 1660 restoration of the monarchy under Charles II waged war against the English Puritans because Charles II implemented the old church and state order.³² Additionally, Anglican loyalists drove the king to restore religious conformity through several legal statutes.³³ For starters, the Clarendon Code³⁴ was a series of four statutes passed between 1661 and 1665 that established the Anglican church, and its goal was to stifle nonconformity.³⁵ The Corporation Act of 1661 required municipal officials to be members of the Anglican communion³⁶ and reject the 1642 Solemn League and Covenant,³⁷ ultimately excluding nonconformists from public office.³⁸ The Act of Uniformity of 1662 required all preachers to implement the modified Book of Common Prayer³⁹ in their worship services.⁴⁰ Roughly two thousand ministers were ejected from the pulpits as a result.⁴¹ The Conventicle Act of 1664 banned nonconformists from public preaching or hosting services in homes.⁴² Lastly, the

³⁰ English Puritanism who advocated that the Church of England was beyond the possibility of internal reform. See Johnson and Pastoor, *Historical Dictionary of the Puritans*, 293. Separationists believed it was their duty to separate from the national church and go on exile. See Beeke and Peterson, *Meet the Puritans*, 856.

³¹ Nonconformity was a Puritan expression that focused on throughout liturgical reform in the church of England. Typically, they would refuse to comply with what they thought were papal superstitions. See Johnson and Pastoor, *Historical Dictionary of the Puritans*, 225-226.

³² Beeke and Peterson, *Meet the Puritans*, 854

³³ Beeke and Peterson, 8.

³⁴ Consists of the Corporation Act (1661), The Act of Uniformity (1662), The Conventicle Act (1664), and the Five-Mile Act of 1665

³⁵ Johnson and Pastoor, *Historical Dictionary of the Puritans*, 80.

³⁶ Johnson and Pastoor, 80.

³⁷ In their efforts for a completely reformed church of England, the Puritans had moments of alliance and success with implementing biblical reform. “The Solemn League and Covenant was a Reformed confession that the majority of Scotland and King James VI subscribed to, and it was an alliance between presbyterians and parliament after the English civil war. King Charles II repealed the confession and copies were publicly burned.” See Johnson and Pastoor, 306.

³⁸ Johnson and Pastoor, *Historical Dictionary of the Puritans*, 80.

³⁹ A book that set forth the liturgy for worship services in the Church of England, it included the administration of the sacraments, and the Puritans had contention for it. See Johnson and Pastoor, 54.

⁴⁰ Johnson and Pastoor, 54.

⁴¹ Johnson and Pastoor, 54.

⁴² Beeke and Peterson, *Meet the Puritans*, 8.

Five-Mile Act of 1665 prohibited ejected nonconformist preachers from teaching within five miles of any incorporated town where they had previously lived.⁴³

Despite facing opposition, The Puritans did not stop from proclaiming biblical truth. They were soul lovers who did not consider the Reformation complete until the population knew Protestant doctrine, such as justification by faith alone.⁴⁴ Ultimately, their desire for a Reformation went beyond the national church; they wanted spiritual reform and transformation in individuals' hearts and minds.⁴⁵ Their scriptural writing is an encouragement for contemporary Christian thought, particularly regarding Christ, and living biblical principles despite persecution. Additionally, with Puritan literature resurfacing in the public domain since the fifties, including eight hundred reprinted books,⁴⁶ readers are finding men passionate and obsessed with the knowledge of God.⁴⁷

i. John Bunyan

John Bunyan (Eg. Fig 1) was a Puritan Nonconformist born in 1628 in Elstow, UK. When reading Bunyan's upbringing, Bunyan was called rebellious as a child, and growing up, he was known for cursing the name of the Lord and having a vulgar mouth.⁴⁸ Bunyan was a tinker and was the first in his family to become literate.⁴⁹ However, Bunyan's life was marked by spiritual doubt, trials, deserts, transformation, and the preaching and ministering of biblical theology. He meticulously wrote his spiritual struggles and conditions in his autobiography *Grace Abounding to the Chief of Sinners*. Bunyan joined the army as a young man and fought for the Parliament⁵⁰

⁴³ Johnson and Pastoor, *Historical Dictionary of the Puritans*, 80.

⁴⁴ Beeke and Reeves, *Following God Fully*, 7.

⁴⁵ Beeke and Reeves, 146.

⁴⁶ Beeke and Reeves, 9.

⁴⁷ Kistler, *Why Read the Puritans Today?* 1.

⁴⁸ Pieter De Vries, "John Bunyan and His Relevance for Today," *Puritan Reformed Journal* 2, no. 1 (January 2010): 67. doi:

<https://search-ebshost-com.lib-proxy.fullerton.edu/login.aspx?direct=true&db=aph&AN=120001854&site=ehost-live&scope=site>.

⁴⁹ Geoff Thomas, "John Bunyan: His Life, Writing, and Influence," *Puritan Reformed Journal* 6, no. 2 (July 2014): 53. doi:

<https://search-ebshost-com.lib-proxy.fullerton.edu/login.aspx?direct=true&db=aph&AN=97766902&site=ehost-live&scope=site>.

⁵⁰ Thomas, John Bunyan: His Life, Writing, and Influence, 54.

in the English Civil War.⁵¹ Bunyan had a near-death experience when a fellow soldier stepped forward at a war zone in the place of Bunyan, and he got shot instead.⁵²

Fig 1. John Bunyan, *Pilgrim's Progress (Parts 1 & 2): Updated, Modern English. More Than 100 illustrations*, (Aneko Press. 2015, Apple Books), 339.

In addition, Bunyan was exposed to the Christian gospel during the army, twice on Sundays, and there were Puritan ministers every Thursday.⁵³ Shortly after the Civil War, Bunyan married his first wife, whose name remains unknown, in 1648,⁵⁴ and she was an orphan.⁵⁵ His first wife had a father who was a godly man who would reprove and correct sin in his house and neighborhood.⁵⁶ His first wife also had two books his father left her: *The Plain Man's Pathway*

⁵¹ Johnson and Pastoor, *Historical Dictionary of the Puritans*, 118.

⁵² John Bunyan, *Grace Abounding to the Chief of Sinners - Updated Edition: A Brief Account of God's Exceeding Mercy Through Christ to His Poor Servant, John Bunyan*, (Aneko Press, 2018, Apple Books), 34.

⁵³ Thomas, *John Bunyan: His Life, Writing, and Influence*, 54.

⁵⁴ Beeke and Peterson, *Meet the Puritans*, 103.

⁵⁵ De Vries, *John Bunyan and His Relevant for Today*, 69.

⁵⁶ John Bunyan, *Grace Abounding to the Chief of Sinners*, 35.

and *The Practice of Piety*. Through reading the books with his wife, Bunyan started growing desires for Christianity.⁵⁷ Bunyan also changed his lifestyle through his first wife by not cussing, reading the Bible, and attending church with his first wife.⁵⁸ During church services, he would speak and sing like others in the congregation, but he kept his wicked life.⁵⁹

Bunyan also began growing a burden on his spirit after his preacher's sermons at his church, thinking he made them on purpose to show him his evil ways.⁶⁰ Despite Bunyan appearing outwardly religious, Bunyan was not spiritually transformed inwardly, and he came to that realization after overhearing three Christian women talking while he was doing tinker work in Bedford. He realized that the woman speaking had something he did not have, and that moment was when he got a glimpse of his religious hypocrisy.⁶¹ Bunyan wrote that the encounter made him doubt his condition, and with all of his thoughts of religion and salvation, the new birth never entered his mind.⁶² Bunyan was also no stranger to spiritual warfare, particularly of his mind. Questions of God's character, His word, and Christianity being the 'true' religion plagued him for a season, and he was also acquainted with blasphemies against God that were poured onto his spirit.⁶³ Like his main character in *The Pilgrim's Progress*, Bunyan walked through the valley of the shadow of death and experienced 'suggestive and distressing blasphemies whispered into his ear.'⁶⁴

In 1651, Bunyan was introduced to John Gifford and his church⁶⁵ after sharing his struggles and condition to the people of Bedford,⁶⁶ which would later lead Bunyan to repentance and faith.⁶⁷ However, one day Bunyan's spiritual burden that discouraged him ceased when he was walking through a field, and he meditated on the righteousness of Christ.⁶⁸ The experience showed him the Christ who sits on the right hand of God in heaven.⁶⁹ After Bunyan had seen

⁵⁷ John Bunyan, *Grace Abounding to the Chief of Sinners*, 35.

⁵⁸ De Vries, *John Bunyan and His Relevant for Today*, 69.

⁵⁹ John Bunyan, *Grace Abounding to the Chief of Sinners*, 35.

⁶⁰ John Bunyan, 37.

⁶¹ De Vries, *John Bunyan and His Relevant for Today*, 69.

⁶² John Bunyan, *Grace Abounding to the Chief of Sinners*, 43.

⁶³ John Bunyan, *Grace Abounding to the Chief of Sinners*, 53.

⁶⁴ John Bunyan, *Pilgrim's Progress (Parts 1 & 2): Updated, Modern English. More Than 100 illustrations*, (Aneko Press. 2015, Apple Books), 74.

⁶⁵ Beeke and Peterson, *Meet the Puritans*, 103.

⁶⁶ John Bunyan, *Grace Abounding to the Chief of Sinners*, 50.

⁶⁷ Beeke and Peterson, *Meet the Puritans*, 103.

⁶⁸ John Bunyan, *Grace Abounding to the Chief of Sinners*, 76.

⁶⁹ John Bunyan, *Grace Abounding to the Chief of Sinners*, 76.

Jesus Christ's worth at the field, he began his call to Christian ministry after others told him God had given him the gift to teach and edify others from God's Holy Word,⁷⁰ and they also desired him to lead meetings.⁷¹ Bunyan began preaching in congregations in Bedford in 1655, and he was known to be acquainted with the faith and preached to men's hearts and minds.⁷² Bunyan also published several books, including *A Few Sighs from Hell* that was 50,000 words.⁷³ By the age of thirty, Bunyan's reputation as a preacher and writer spread throughout England,⁷⁴ and he was widowed after the death of his first wife, leaving him to care for four children, including his first daughter Mary, who was blind.⁷⁵

At the peak of Bunyan's ministry, he remarried his second wife, Elizabeth,⁷⁶ amid the restoration of the monarchy in 1660. Persecution was peaking for Nonconformists, and the Clarendon Codes led to Bunyan's two arrests. His first arrest was in 1660 for preaching without a license and the right from the king to preach.⁷⁷ He was imprisoned until 1672, during this time he began writing part one of *The Pilgrim's Progress*.⁷⁸ After his first imprisonment, Bunyan was anointed as the pastor of a Bedford congregation in 1672.⁷⁹ As a pastor, he would visit the sick, intervene in brotherly conflicts, and counsel people's anxieties.⁸⁰ His second imprisonment was in 1674, and he finished part one of *The Pilgrim's Progress* during his second sentence.⁸¹ His release was in 1677,⁸² and part one of *The Pilgrim's Progress* was published in 1678.⁸³

After his second imprisonment, Bunyan continued to preach and publish books. His nonconformity was intolerable to the English authorities, and he and his congregation needed to meet in fields due to the English authorities closing down his congregation house.⁸⁴ Bunyan also wrote and published part two of *The Pilgrim's Progress*, which was published in 1684.⁸⁵

⁷⁰ John Bunyan, *Grace Abounding to the Chief of Sinners*, 83.

⁷¹ John Bunyan, *Grace Abounding to the Chief of Sinners*, 83.

⁷² Beeke and Jones, *A Puritan Theology*, 714.

⁷³ Thomas, John Bunyan: His Life, Writing, and Influence, 57.

⁷⁴ Thomas, 58.

⁷⁵ Thomas, 58.

⁷⁶ Beeke and Peterson, *Meet the Puritans*, 105.

⁷⁷ Beeke and Peterson, 105.

⁷⁸ De Vries, John Bunyan and His Relevant for Today, 70.

⁷⁹ Beeke and Peterson, *Meet the Puritans*, 106.

⁸⁰ John Bunyan, *Grace Abounding to the Chief of Sinners*, 19.

⁸¹ Beeke and Peterson, *Meet the Puritans*, 107.

⁸² Beeke and Peterson, 107.

⁸³ John Bunyan, *Grace Abounding to the Chief of Sinners*, 21.

⁸⁴ John Bunyan, 23.

⁸⁵ John Bunyan, 22.

Although the monarchy's policies, such as the act of uniformity and the conventicle act, cost Bunyan a significant number of years in prison, Bunyan faithfully lived according to his convictions concerning the Christian faith. He died in 1688 after catching a fever when traveling in cold weather.⁸⁶ Trials and success marked Bunyan's life, but he was consistent.⁸⁷ He remained faithful in the race until the end, where he raised his hands to heaven and cried, "Take me, for I come to Thee!"⁸⁸ to meet the Savior he cherished and served.

2. Puritan Theology

Regarding what the Puritans preached, they were a group of scriptural people.⁸⁹ The focus of the Puritan preacher and writer was to reform all aspects of one's life according to the standard of the Bible and through Jesus Christ as revealed in the Bible.⁹⁰ Using the Bible as the basis of their preaching, the topics were straight from the Bible. Some of the issues the Puritans emphasized were the "centrality of the church in the redemptive work of Christ" and that "man's justified before God by faith alone in Christ"⁹¹ and that "man's justified before God by faith alone in Christ."⁹² The Puritans also heavily preached on the Trinity⁹³ and church government⁹⁴ amidst their efforts of liturgical reform in the Church of England.

Puritan Theology is an enriching investment for today partly because of their knowledge and application of the Scriptures,⁹⁵ their doctrinal focus on Christ,⁹⁶ and their application of Scriptural principles in persecution and pain.⁹⁷ Victorian Preacher said that next to the Bible, he valued Bunyan's *The Pilgrim's Progress* and has read it at least a hundred times,⁹⁸ and he said the

⁸⁶ Beeke and Peterson, *Meet the Puritans*, 108.

⁸⁷ John Bunyan, *Grace Abounding to the Chief of Sinners*, 24.

⁸⁸ Beeke and Peterson, *Meet the Puritans*, 108.

⁸⁹ Beeke and Reeves, *Following God Fully*, 4.

⁹⁰ Beeke and Reeves, 6.

⁹¹ Beeke and Reeves, 13.

⁹² Beeke and Reeves, *Following God Fully*, 13.

⁹³ Beeke and Peterson, *Meet the Puritans*, preface xvii.

⁹⁴ Beeke and Peterson, preface xvii.

⁹⁵ Beeke and Reeves, *Following God Fully*, 146

⁹⁶ Beeke and Reeves, 147.

⁹⁷ Beeke and Reeves, 148.

⁹⁸ Charles Hadden Spurgeon, *Pictures From Pilgrim's Progress: A Commentary on Portions of John Bunyan's Immortal Allegory*, (Monergism Books, 2021), page 8,

<https://www.monergism.com/thethreshold/sdg/spurgeon/Pictures%20from%20Pilgrim's%20Progres%20-%20C.%20H.%20Spurgeon.pdf>.

secret of its freshness is its composition from the Scriptures.⁹⁹ Furthermore, from Puritan literature, one should expect a doctrinal exegesis on biblical topics regarding the doctrine of salvation, Christ, and the church, which is an excellent source because of their commitment to biblical truth.

The Five Solas of the Reformation

Before examining Puritan theology, it is essential to highlight the grounds of their theological framework that goes back to the roots of the Protestant Reformation. Reformers Calvin¹⁰⁰ and Martin Luther heavily influenced the Puritans' theology. What came out of the Reformation can be known as a five-summary point of the theological convictions that reflected the spirit of the Reformation and its reformers alongside the approach the Protestants pushed for the interpretation of the Bible. They are known as the five solas and the word "sola" alone in Latin. The five solas were not disconnected but an integrated understanding of biblical truth.¹⁰¹ The five solas are the following:

- i. *Sola Scriptura* = Scripture alone
- ii. *Sola Fide* = Faith alone
- iii. *Sola Gratia* = Grace alone
- iv. *Solus Christus* = Christ alone
- v. *Soli Deo Gloria* = The glory of God alone¹⁰²

The five solas summarized the teachings of the reformers. They were not explicit taglines during the Reformation. However, they summarize the doctrinal standards of the Protestant Reformation, and its defenders. In the paper, *Sola Scriptura*, *Sola Fide*, and *Solus Christus* are highlighted upon examining the textual evidence from *The Pilgrim's Progress*. Given that the Puritans were scriptural people, their teachings on the doctrine of salvation will be best

⁹⁹ Spurgeon, *Pictures from Pilgrim's Progress*, 9.

¹⁰⁰ The Puritans were strongly influenced by Calvinism. See Johnson and Pastoor, *Historical Dictionary of the Puritans*, 267. Their doctrine is often described as a kind of vigorous Calvinism. See Beeke and Reeves, *Following God Fully*, 13.

¹⁰¹ Wells, *The Courage to Be Protestant*, 21.

¹⁰² See Matthew Barrett, *God's Word Alone: The Authority of Scripture*, (Harper Collins & Zondervan, 2016), 9.

understood through Sola Scriptura. The doctrinal tenets of salvation and the church will be understood through Solus Christus and Sola Fide.

Sola Scriptura

The Puritans completely adhered to several elements in the teaching of Sola Scriptura. For starters, Sola Scriptura teaches that the Bible is the canonized¹⁰³ word from God. Because it is the word of God, the Bible is sufficient, credible, and has authority as God's revelation. The sufficiency of Scripture connects to the character of God. The Bible mentions that all Scripture is God-breathed,¹⁰⁴ and therefore, it is fundamentally truthful because its divine author is a God of truth.¹⁰⁵ That said, following exclusively without additional traditions from secondary sources is sufficient. Overall, the basis of *Sola Scriptura*, the first Sola, demonstrates that all biblical doctrine and instruction branches from the Bible. The Puritans believed the Bible had clear instructions on Christ,¹⁰⁶ and their teachings expounded those biblical principles to instruct the church. By emphasizing Sola Scriptura, the doctrinal basis for the church becomes clear and grounded in biblical truth.

Regarding the doctrine of salvation, its explanations and teachings from the Sola Scriptura basis point to Jesus Christ as the salvation focus. God speaking in the Bible is also a communication of information, followed by an action.¹⁰⁷ For example, a declaration and application demonstrate God's communication on salvific topics. John 3:16¹⁰⁸ for instance, says "for God so loved the world, that He gave His only Son, that whoever believes in Him should not perish but have eternal life." In the following verse, God declares that He loved humanity enough to send Christ for anyone to believe in Him. Furthermore, the "gave" was Christ dying on the cross and resurrecting three days later. As Romans 5:8¹⁰⁹ reiterates, "but God shows His love

¹⁰³ Canon means "authoritative collection of Christian scripture comprising the accepted book of the Old and New Testament." See Dowley, *Introduction to the History of Christianity*, 645.

¹⁰⁴ The verse speaks of the divine origin of the Bible being God. Insert Bible verse here with EVS commentary. See Crossway Bibles. *The ESV Study Bible. English Standard Version*. Wheaton, IL. 2008. 2342

¹⁰⁵ Barret, *God's Word Alone*, 29.

¹⁰⁶ The Puritans would turn to the new testament when preaching about Christ. See Beeke and Reeves, *Following God Fully*, 147.

¹⁰⁷ Barret, *God's Word Alone*, 305.

¹⁰⁸ In context, the verse explains how it is possible for someone to gain eternal life. See Crossway Bibles, *The ESV Study Bible, English Standard Version*, (Wheaton, IL, 2008), 2025.

¹⁰⁹ God's love of sending Christ was not on any basis of human goodness. Crossway Bibles, *The ESV Study Bible, English Standard Version*, (Wheaton, IL, 2008), 2165.

for us in that while we were still sinners, Christ died for us.” In the example, God communicates He loved humanity, and the action was Christ dying on humanity's behalf.

Another example of the declaration and application of God’s word regarding the doctrine of salvation includes the aftereffects of the death and resurrection of Christ. God pronounced the sinner not guilty, and they are called righteousness because of Christ’s righteousness.¹¹⁰ God communicates a redemptive narrative from the front to the back cover of the Bible. The narrative includes the topics of sin and its restoration. In the Bible’s storyline, God has established covenants that would, in return, enable humans to have communion with God.¹¹¹ The cross and resurrection of Jesus is the “inauguration of the new covenant, whereby God communicates eternal life to his covenant recipients.”¹¹² The covental words of God produce a saving action¹¹³ and do not portray sole information, but they “bring into existence a new state of affairs.”¹¹⁴ With the new covenant in Christ, its recipients have a new life and identity in Christ¹¹⁵ according to Scripture.¹¹⁶

Sola Fide

As the second sola, sola fide teaches that salvation "does not come from looking at our own works of righteousness, but from looking outside ourselves to another the person and work of Jesus Christ."¹¹⁷ Additionally, sola fide also teaches that living a moral life, good works, or religious deeds will be enough to justify a sinner before God.¹¹⁸ Hebrews 11:1 describes faith being “the assurance of things hoped for, the conviction of things not seen.”¹¹⁹ With faith, there is an object in which one places one's trust. To the Christians, the object of their faith is for Christ

¹¹⁰ Barret, *God's Word Alone*, 306.

¹¹¹ Barret, 150.

¹¹² Barret, 160.

¹¹³ Barret, 306.

¹¹⁴ Barret, 306.

¹¹⁵ Barret, *God's Word Alone*, 306.

¹¹⁶ 2 Corinthians 5:17 talks about how redemption in Christ is living a new identity by the death of Christ and the power of the Spirit. Crossway Bibles, *The ESV Study Bible*, English Standard Version, (Wheaton, IL, 2008), 2230.

¹¹⁷ Thomas R. Schreiner, *Faith Alone: The Doctrine of Justification: What the Reformers Taught and Why It Still Matters*, (Grand Rapids Michigan: Zondervan. 2015), 15.

¹¹⁸ Terry L. Johnson, *The Case for Traditional Protestantism: The Solas of the Reformation*, (Edinburgh UK: Banner of Truth Trust. 2004), 77.

¹¹⁹ Faith is not grounded in wishful thinking, it is grounded in the future, something that is not yet seen but has been promised by God. Crossway Bibles, *The ESV Study Bible*, English Standard Version, (Wheaton, IL, 2008), 2379.

to stand right before God.¹²⁰ For instance, faith in Christ is the grounds in salvation,¹²¹ not misplaced faith in anything. Characteristics of a Christian not only include faith, but also belief and trust¹²² in Christ.

Solus Christus

With an emphasis on searching for answers and meanings in the Scriptures, its principles all point and talk about one theme: one person. Solus Christus is the fourth solo, focusing on the conviction of the exclusivity of His identity and the sufficiency of His work.¹²³ Solus Christus as the anchor is necessary to understand the key to interpret scriptures and Christ as the object of one's faith.¹²⁴ Regarding Christ's exclusive identity and sufficient work, it is about His nature as both fully man and God, in addition to his death and resurrection being enough to save the Christian faith. Without the exclusiveness of Christ's identity, God's perfect standard would not be met,¹²⁵ and without the standards being met, there would be no reconciliation with God.¹²⁶ Regarding the sufficiency of His work, the exclusiveness of Christ's identity enabled the sufficient work on the cross. For example, with Christ as fully God, He walked in perfect obedience to God's will for humanity, and it is a reminder that humans are disobedient to God's perfect standard¹²⁷ in the Mosaic law. With Christ as sinless, it qualifies Christ as the mediator, representative, and substitute who bears individual sin and guilt¹²⁸ through propitiating¹²⁹ God's wrath,¹³⁰ and later bringing justification.¹³¹

¹²⁰ Schreiner, *Faith Alone*, 132.

¹²¹ Johnson, *The Case for Traditional Protestantism*, 83.

¹²² Schreiner, *Faith Alone*, 119.

¹²³ Wellum, *Christ Alone*, 13.

¹²⁴ Wellum, 14.

¹²⁵ 1 Peter 2:22 talks about how the sinlessness of Christ enabled for Him to be the substitutionary atonement for sinners. Crossway Bibles, *The ESV Study Bible*, English Standard Version, (Wheaton, IL, 2008), 2409.

¹²⁶ Wellum, 35.

¹²⁷ Wellum, 244.

¹²⁸ Wellum, *Christ Alone*, 140.

¹²⁹ Propitiation in the paper is defined as "turning aside a person's wrath or anger." See Wellum, 234.

¹³⁰ Wellum, 130.

¹³¹ Wellum, 130.

The Westminster Confession of Faith

As previously mentioned, the Puritans used catechisms and creeds to defend biblical topics from their religious opponents.¹³² In their liturgical battle with the church and state after the English Civil War, one hundred Puritan leaders gathered at Westminster Abbey to create a biblical creed for the church.¹³³ Westminster Confession was prompted by a desire to stray from the Apocrypha and distance the church from Catholic traditions.¹³⁴ The Westminster Confession deemed the Apocrypha as having no authority in the life of a Christian.¹³⁵ The Westminster Confession of Faith also reflects the doctrinal standard produced by the Reformation, which included the five solas. It also reflects the English Calvinism of the Puritans in the sixteenth and seventeenth century.¹³⁶ The Puritan's reverent view of God came from their high view of the Scriptures.¹³⁷ For example, in chapter 1 concerning the Holy Scriptures, point nine states that "the infallible standard for interpreting the Bible is the Bible itself. And so many questions about the true and complete sense of a passage in the Bible (which is a unified whole) can be answered by referring to other passages which speak more plainly."¹³⁸

Soteriology

Soteriology is the study and teaching¹³⁹ of salvation.¹⁴⁰ Similar to various areas in Christian study, the Puritans placed an emphasis on the role of the Holy Spirit,¹⁴¹ the third person of the trinity,¹⁴² with a trinitarian context, specifically with the three distinct persons sharing equal works,¹⁴³ with each one as author of a particular work.¹⁴⁴ With those specific works, the

¹³² Johnson and Pastoor, *Historical Dictionary of the Puritans*, 290.

¹³³ Beeke and Peterson, *Meet the Puritans*, 8-9.

¹³⁴ Johnson and Pastoor, *Historical Dictionary of the Puritans*, 290.

¹³⁵ McClure and Rollinson, *The Westminster Confession of Faith*, 4.

¹³⁶ Johnson and Pastoor, *Historical Dictionary of the Puritans*, 70-71.

¹³⁷ Kistler, *Why Read the Puritans Today?* 17.

¹³⁸ McClure and Rollinson, *The Westminster Confession of Faith*, 5.

¹³⁹ Dowley, *Introduction to the History of Christianity*, 654.

¹⁴⁰ Salvation is the state of being forgiven one's sin against God, and it is made possible through the atoning sacrifice of Jesus Christ on the cross. See Johnson and Pastoor, *Historical Dictionary of the Puritans*, 281.

¹⁴¹ Beeke and Jones, *A Puritan Theology*, 419.

¹⁴² God as "three persons, equally. God: the Father. God; the Son, and the Holy Spirit constitute the divine unity." See Dowley, pg. 655.

¹⁴³ Beeke and Jones, *A Puritan Theology*, 422.

¹⁴⁴ Beeke and Peterson, 423.

three persons are coequal in deity and their work of salvation in a believer.¹⁴⁵ According to the Puritans, the Holy Spirit's Spirit's work dwells in the believer,¹⁴⁶ helping them experience the new life in Christ, loving as God loves.¹⁴⁷ Not only is the Holy Spirit the agent in the application of redemption,¹⁴⁸ but it also convicts men of sin and moves them to repentance to embrace Jesus Christ in faith.¹⁴⁹ Additionally, the Puritans also preached from a Christological context in soteriology.¹⁵⁰ Christology is the teaching about the nature of the person of Christ.¹⁵¹ In soteriology, the work of both the Spirit and Son are interchangeable, specifically with the humiliation and exaltation of Christ.¹⁵² Subjects such as the virgin birth are crucial to the sinlessness of Christ because Christ is sinless because He was conceived by the power of the Holy Spirit in Mary's womb.¹⁵³ Jesus' ministry and resurrection were also in the power of the Holy Spirit.¹⁵⁴ Through the Son's perfect obedience and sacrifice, Jesus satisfied the justice of God's Father required against sin, all through the Spirit.¹⁵⁵

Human Sin

One of the essential doctrines in Christianity and the identity of the redemptive church is the fall of man, also known as original sin.¹⁵⁶ The fall of man is traced back to Genesis 3¹⁵⁷ at the Garden of Eden, where Adam and Eve disobeyed God by eating the apple from the tree of good and evil. The fall of men set the redemptive stage for Christ and his work on the cross, with

¹⁴⁵ Beeke and Peterson, *Meet the Puritans*, 423.

¹⁴⁶ Beeke and Peterson, 423.

¹⁴⁷ Beeke and Reeves, *Following God Fully*, 57.

¹⁴⁸ McClure and Rollinson, *The Westminster Confession of Faith*, 54

¹⁴⁹ McClure and Rollinson, 54.

¹⁵⁰ Beeke and Jones, *A Puritan Theology*, 423.

¹⁵¹ Dowley, *Introduction to the History of Christianity*, 646.

¹⁵² Beeke and Jones, *A Puritan Theology*, 423.

¹⁵³ McClure and Rollinson, *The Westminster Confession of Faith*, 15.

¹⁵⁴ Beeke and Jones, *A Puritan Theology*, 424.

¹⁵⁵ McClure and Rollinson, *The Westminster Confession of Faith*, 16.

¹⁵⁶ Original Sin teaches that the disobedience of one man left humanity destroyed. The first man (Adam) revolted against the command of God to not eat fruit from the tree of knowledge. Because of Adam's heinous crime, Adam's fall produced the nature of sin. See Jean Calvin, *Institutes of the Christian Religion*. Translated by Henry Beveridge, (Peabody, Mass: Hendrickson Publishers, 2008), 149.

¹⁵⁷ Genesis 3 is the recount of Adam and Eve's deception, and ultimately their disregard to God's instructions, which was an act of willful rebellion. Crossway Bibles, *The ESV Study Bible*, English Standard Version, (Wheaton, IL, 2008), 55.

God's declaration in verse fifteen: "he shall bruise your head, and you shall bruise his heel."¹⁵⁸ Otherwise, if Christ had not suffered and tortured to death on the cross for the sins of the world, then it was all in vain. Without the pillar of original sin and the fall of man,¹⁵⁹ there is no need for divine reconciliation before God in Christ and His death and resurrection.¹⁶⁰ Without divine reconciliation, it implies that Christ suffered and was tortured to death in vain. In addition, the Puritans felt that humanity fell from their original state of righteousness and fellowship with God, becoming dead in sin, and their descendants inherited the same death in sin and corruption.¹⁶¹ With the original corruption, man is pardoned and forgiven in Jesus Christ.¹⁶² The restoration of mankind through Jesus also includes his resurrection, for 1 Corinthians 15:19¹⁶³ states that Christians would be the most pitied people if Christ had not risen.

The Atonement

The study of the cross of Christ falls under the doctrine of the atonement¹⁶⁴ The cross of Christ is crucial in the sufficiency of Christ and his work, as declared in Solus Christus. With atonement theory, it needs to align with what God had revealed Himself to be.¹⁶⁵ With that said, going back to the source of biblical text to see what God's declarations and actions are is an excellent place to start with atonement theory. The Reformers and the Puritans preached the

¹⁵⁸ The ESV Study Bible states that modern interpretations talk about the "natural hostility that exists between men and snakes." Traditionally, the defeat of the serpent is by a future descendant of a woman. The "he" fulfills the biblical framework of Jesus' defeat of satan, and Christ coming from the descendants of Mary being a descendant of Mary and Joseph. Crossway Bibles, The ESV Study Bible, English Standard Version, (Wheaton, IL, 2008), 56.

¹⁵⁹ "The Puritans had a high view of the grace of God in the salvation of sinners because, in the first place, they had a high view of sin." See Beeke and Jones, *A Puritan Theology*, 208. "Sin is such a powerful enemy because it resides in the whole soul of man." See Beeke and Jones, 213. "It is more merely a choice, it is a condition of depravity inherited from the fall of Adam in Paradise, a depravity that makes us unfit for God, holiness, and heaven." See Beeke and Jones, 915.

¹⁶⁰ That is because "all humanity is in Adam and therefore under the power and penalty of sin." See Wellum, *Christ Alone*, 175.

¹⁶¹ McClure and Rollinson, *The Westminster Confession of Faith*, 12.

¹⁶² McClure and Rollinson, 12.

¹⁶³ The resurrection demonstrated the effective substitutionary sacrifice for sinners. Without Christ being raised, sin was not paid. Crossway Bibles, The ESV Study Bible, English Standard Version, (Wheaton, IL, 2008), 2214.

¹⁶⁴ Atonement, as used in the paper, can be defined as the "reconciliation between God and humanity required because of the absolute holiness of God and the sinfulness of men and women. As human beings are incapable of achieving atonement, it is a work of God's grace, through the death of Jesus Chrsts, for human sin" See Dowley, *Introduction to the History of Christianity*, 645.

¹⁶⁵ Schreiner, *Faith Alone*, 26.

atonement of Christ as penal substitution.¹⁶⁶ Penal substitution meets the requirements of one taking humanity's place to pay and satisfy the penalty of sin. Part of substitution theory involves imputation, which is humanity's ungodliness and unrighteousness being revoked to Christ. In return, Christ's righteousness is reckoned on account of the sinner.¹⁶⁷

With the satisfaction of Christ's death through the imputation of man's unrighteousness placed on Christ, the imputation of Christ's righteousness falls into the justification of the sinner. Justification is when there is the forgiveness of sins and a right to eternal life.¹⁶⁸ Because of Christ's perfect obedience to God's law and voluntarily enduring torment to the point of death,¹⁶⁹ it is the grounds in which a sinner has rights to heaven.¹⁷⁰ Christ dying for one's sins is a fundamental doctrine for Christianity because, without the death and resurrection of Jesus, there is no Christianity or salvation in spiritual transformation, and the church would stay dead in sin.¹⁷¹ However, with the penalty of sin being paid on the cross, it destroys the power of death that could not hold Christ.¹⁷²

Newness in Life

Regarding Soteriology, it takes repentance or a turning away from one's old life and sins to face the way of Christ and faith to empower one to continue forward even when the spiritual journey in Christ gets hard.¹⁷³ Repentance is also ongoing, enabling a believer to communicate with God. For it is "inconsistent with the sanctity of God's nature to pardon a sinner while he is

¹⁶⁶ The Reformers and its heirs viewed the atonement through "Penal Substitution" "Penal refers to the sorry state of the human race in Adam in which we stand under God's judgment and the penalty of death. See Wellum, *Christ Alone*, Pg 175. "Substitution refers to the power on and work of our Lord Jesus Christ who acts on our behalf in his death on the cross." See Wellum, 176. "In death in particular, Christ stood in our place, took God's demand for our ridsions upon himself, and paid our debt by receiving the penalty we deserve." See Wellum, 176.

¹⁶⁷ Beeke and Jones, *A Puritan Theology*, 36.

¹⁶⁸ Beeke and Jones, 362.

¹⁶⁹ McClure and Rollinson, *The Westminster Confession of Faith*, 15.

¹⁷⁰ Beeke and Jones, *A Puritan Theology*, 362-363.

¹⁷¹ "Christ's resurrection is evidence his work to save his people from their sins has been achieved." Wellum, *Christ Alone*. "Christ's resurrection inaugurates the new creation and because of the resurrection, salvation has been accomplished" Schreiner, *Faith Alone*, 149.

¹⁷² Schreiner, 149.

¹⁷³ "Repentance is the twin sister of faith - we cannot think of the one without the other, and so repentance would be conjoined with faith" John Murray, *Redemption Accomplished and Applied*, (Grand Rapids Michigan: William B. Eerdmans Publishing Company. 2015), 89.

"Conversion is simply another name for repentance and faith conjoined and would therefore be inclosed in repentance and faith" Murray, *Redemption Accomplished and Applied*, 89.

still in the act of rebellion."¹⁷⁴ However, repentance gives access to knowledge of Christ because, with a hatred of sin, it is the beginning of repentance as a sinner groans and is burdened.¹⁷⁵ With repentance, it is an element of the new birth, also known as regeneration. Regeneration, as the Puritans preached, is a believer's experience of spiritual renewal and transformation with conversion, faith, and repentance.¹⁷⁶ The Puritans also preached that regeneration is the start of a believer's life, which is required to be born of the Holy Spirit.¹⁷⁷ Through fellowship in Christ, the believer is preserved from the temptations of Satan, the world, and their old carnal nature.¹⁷⁸ The preservation of believers depends on the mediation of Jesus Christ and the indwelling of the Spirit.¹⁷⁹

Ecclesiology

Ecclesiology is the study of the church.¹⁸⁰ According to the Westminster Confession of Faith, the church is universal and invisible under the headship of Christ.¹⁸¹ With Jesus as the head of the church, it means that her being is under the influence of Jesus. That means the church is derived from Him, and all flows from Jesus as the source.¹⁸² With that said, the Bible is a communication from God, "telling them of truths and doctrines, through the right appreciation of which they may be fashioned into a spiritual society, with divinely authorized powers and ordinances and office-bearers,- an outward and public witness for God on the earth, and an instrument for the edification of the people of Christ."¹⁸³ As the Westminster Confession states, the universal church consists of people worldwide who profess the true religion.¹⁸⁴ The people who are members of the church are sinners once lost and interrupted by sin, who are restored through a Savior.¹⁸⁵

¹⁷⁴ Thomas Watson, *The Doctrine of Repentance*, (Monergism Books, 1688), 67, <https://www.monergism.com/thethreshold/sdg/watson/The%20Doctrine%20of%20Repentance%20-%20Thomas%20Watson.pdf>.

¹⁷⁵ Calvin, *Institutes of the Christian Religion*, 398.

¹⁷⁶ Beeke and Reeves, *Following God Fully*, 63.

¹⁷⁷ Beeke and Reeves, 63.

¹⁷⁸ McClure and Rollinson, *The Westminster Confession of Faith*, 27.

¹⁷⁹ McClure and Rollinson, 27.

¹⁸⁰ Dowley, *Introduction to the History of Christianity*, 647.

¹⁸¹ McClure and Rollinson, *The Westminster Confession of Faith*, 44.

¹⁸² Bannerman, *The Church of Christ*, 233.

¹⁸³ Bannerman, *The Church of Christ*, 17.

¹⁸⁴ McClure and Rollinson, *The Westminster Confession of Faith*, 44.

¹⁸⁵ Bannerman, *The Church of Christ*, 396.

Through the restoration of the savior, they are also identified as saints, believers justified by the faith of Jesus Christ.¹⁸⁶ As saints of Christ, the church has been given external rights and privileges as part of their newness in life.¹⁸⁷ Some external privileges include fellowship, communion with the congregation, and being part of their blessing during the saints' Christian walk.¹⁸⁸ Because of the imputation of the righteousness of Christ, believers are also perfected in holiness and received in heaven to behold the face of God and wait for the redemption of their bodies.¹⁸⁹

One of the tools Christ uses to edify His church is the office-bearers. Jesus also appointed the same officers of a church to exercise their authority.¹⁹⁰ The head of the church is the pastor, who governs the church while keeping guard to keep safe.¹⁹¹ The Puritans highlighted a pastor's traits, including "the necessity of personal godliness and soundness in the faith."¹⁹² John Owen's book *The True Nature of a Gospel Church* also highlights traits of a pastor in a biblical church. One of the highlights for the pastor is to have a "compassionate suffering with all the members of the church in all their trials and troubles, whether internal or external, belongs unto them in the discharge of their office."¹⁹³

3. What is *The Pilgrim's Progress*?

The Pilgrim's Progress is a two-part allegory written by John Bunyan. As the first one in his family to become literate,¹⁹⁴ Bunyan learned to read through a school scholarship¹⁹⁵ later in his life and wrote most of *The Pilgrim's Progress* without effort¹⁹⁶ during his first imprisonment. Due to his fervent spirit with teaching, the Word of God was described as a burning fire in Bunyan's heart.¹⁹⁷ Being written chiefly in prison, Bunyan got no materials from stores and no

¹⁸⁶ Murray, *Redemption Accomplished and Applied*, 166.

¹⁸⁷ Bannerman, *The Church of Christ*, 28.

¹⁸⁸ "There is an external provision of ordinances made by Christ and His church, ensuring both outward privilege and blessing, and there is a compliance with this invitation on the part of those who profess their faith in Christ and join themselves to His church, and the actual enjoyment and experience of the privileges so promised, - in so far, at least, as they are of an external or temporary kind." Bannerman, 51.

¹⁸⁹ McClure and Rollinson, *The Westminster Confession of Faith*, 52.

¹⁹⁰ John Owen, *The True Nature of a Gospel Church*, (Monergism Books, 1689, Apple Books Epub), 88.

¹⁹¹ Calvin, *Institutes of the Christian Religion*, 701.

¹⁹² Beeke and Jones, *A Puritan Theology*, 647.

¹⁹³ John Owen, *The True Nature of a Gospel Church*, 180.

¹⁹⁴ Thomas, John Bunyan: His Life, Writing, and Influence, 53.

¹⁹⁵ Thomas, John Bunyan: His Life, Writing, and Influence, 53.

¹⁹⁶ John Bunyan, *Grace Abounding to the Chief of Sinners*, 21.

¹⁹⁷ Beeke and Jones, *A Puritan Theology*, 713.

inspiration from many waters, for the book was only made known to people once he finished it.¹⁹⁸ Bunyan wrote about what he knew best, and as Charles Spurgeon described *The Pilgrim's Progress*, “biblical teaching put into the form of a simple yet striking allegory.”¹⁹⁹

The first part reflects Bunyan's experiences as a Christian.²⁰⁰ It focuses on an individual named Christian. Several Christians' experiences parallel Bunyan's journey, particularly when encountering the righteousness of Christ after a storm of doubts. Christian is on a journey from the City of Destruction to the Celestial City. Like Bunyan's burdens of sin, Christian has a significant burden on his back, crying for a way to be free. Christian ultimately finds freedom from his burden at the foot of the cross after crossing the Wicket Gate, and the remainder of part one follows Christian on his new journey after his burden falls with like-minded pilgrims such as Faithful and Hopeful accompanying him.

Part two focuses on Christiana and her children Mathew, James, and Joseph, the children and wife of Christian from Part One. While part one was a story of an individual pilgrim, part two is pastoral. Contrary to part one, Bunyan paid particular attention to believers who were weak in faith.²⁰¹ He also focused on the role of women²⁰¹ and their pleasant journey toward a home (Celestial City).²⁰² Part two follows a similar plot pattern: Christiana embarks herself and her kids on the same pilgrimage her husband walked after a conviction and calling from the King of the Celestial City inviting her to where He and Christian are. Like Christian in part one, Christiana and her kids are accompanied by a diverse group of pilgrims, such as Mr. Feeble Mind, who are all under the spiritual guidance of Mr. Great Heart.

As previously mentioned, *The Pilgrim's Progress* is an allegory. It is an allegory where each detail has meaning, and readers can “identify with Christian and his struggles, sorrows, and joys.”²⁰³ Bunyan used the allegorical methods as a didactic or rhetorical instrument as a persuasive way of expressing things known.²⁰⁴ Through biblical imagery, Bunyan uses Christianity as a central agent to make metaphoric assertions about religious conversion and

¹⁹⁸ John Bunyan, *Grace Abounding to the Chief of Sinners*, 21.

¹⁹⁹ Spurgeon, *Pictures from Pilgrim's Progress*, 9.

²⁰⁰ De Vries, John Bunyan and His Relevant for Today, 68.

²⁰¹ De Vries, John Bunyan and His Relevance for Today, 68.

²⁰² John Bunyan, *Grace Abounding to the Chief of Sinners*, 22.

²⁰³ De Vries, John Bunyan and His Relevant for Today, 68.

²⁰⁴ Charles William Baird, *John Bunyan: A Study in Narrative Technique*, 3-24 (Port Washington, N.Y: Kennikat Press, 1977), 14.

growth²⁰⁵ according to the theology that is inspired by the Westminster Confession of Faith.²⁰⁶ With Bunyan's library being the Bible²⁰⁷ and experiencing the ups and downs of Christian life,²⁰⁸ he was able to meet sinners and saints where they were²⁰⁹ in their downfalls and successes in his book.

Textual Evidence

Bunyan demonstrated the doctrinal principles and standards regarding salvation and the church according to the Reformation in various allegories in both parts. Pastorally, Bunyan presented several allegories as a means of shepherding encouragement regarding Christian struggles and weaknesses. The allegories in the textual evidence highlight the tenets of Puritan theology and their roots in the Reformation, emphasizing doctrinal principles of the cross and Christ. They are ordered in the following way: allegories demonstrating soteriological elements such as sin, salvation, and redemption; allegories with ecclesiological aspects of fellowship, spiritual blessings, and church leadership; and lastly, allegories that Bunyan from a pastoral heart, highlighted to showcase weaknesses that can plague Christian believers in their new lives, however, the doctrine of salvation and church fellowship providing aid and remedy to the struggles.

1. *Human Nature Before Christ*

Symbolic implications of the fall of man are in the form of locations from which the pilgrims originated. In the story, the pilgrim gives a brief synopsis of their testimony and upbringing; part of the testimony explains their town of origin. Bunyan communicates that before being restored to Christ, each person's origins all derive from Adam, with original sin corrupting their spiritual condition. For starters, Christians came from the City of Destruction, and as Christian had read from his book, which in the allegory is the Bible,²¹⁰ the City of

²⁰⁵ Baird, *John Bunyan: A Study in Narrative Technique*, 13.

²⁰⁶ Thomas, *John Bunyan: His Life, Writing, and Influence*, 61.

²⁰⁷ Beeke and Jones, *A Puritan Theology*, 723.

²⁰⁸ Beeke and Jones, 723.

²⁰⁹ Beeke and Jones, 723.

²¹⁰ When Christian ran into Pliable and Obstinate, Pliable asked Christian if he thought his book was true, and Christian said the book was made by "Him who cannot lie" and it was inspired by Titus 1:2, saying "for the hope of eternal life, which God, who cannot lie, promised long ages ago." John Bunyan, *Pilgrim's Progress (Parts 1 & 2): Updated, Modern English. More Than 100 illustrations*, (Aneko Press. 2015, Apple Books), 13.

Destruction would face the judgment of fire and brimstone.²¹¹ Additionally, Old Honest came from Stupidity, one town beyond the City of Destruction.²¹² One of the pilgrims Christian first encountered, Faithful, said he encountered someone named Adam the First who came from the town of Deceit.²¹³ Adam revealed to Faithful that he had three children, known as the lust of the flesh and eyes and the pride of life.²¹⁴ Because of Adam and Eve's disobedience, sinners are dead in Adam's headship.²¹⁵ However, under the new headship in Christ, a sinner is a redeemed person in Christ, under a new covenant of grace,²¹⁶ for like Christian said, he was named Graceless before entering the gate.²¹⁷

2. *The Wicket Gate*

Even though remnants of part one are autobiographical to the life of Bunyan and his spiritual convictions, the principles of his convictions were grounded in the doctrine of repentance and faith. The wicket gate was small for Christians to see when the Evangelist pointed it at him.²¹⁸ However, in true repentance, “the heart points directly to God just as the compass needle points to the North Pole”²¹⁹ with urgency as Christian demonstrated by knocking more than once or twice.

“Enter by the narrow gate. For the gate is wide and the way is easy that leads to destruction, and those who enter by it are many. For the gate is narrow and the way is hard that leads to life, and those who find it are few.

*Matthew 7:13-14*²²⁰

²¹¹ John Bunyan, *Pilgrim's Progress*, 10.

²¹² John Bunyan, *Pilgrim's Progress*, 262.

²¹³ John Bunyan, *Pilgrim's Progress*, 81.

²¹⁴ John Bunyan, 81.

²¹⁵The doctrine of the immediate imputation of Adam's guilt was typically understood to provide the ground for the transmission of indwelling or inherent sin.” See Beeke and Jones, *A Puritan Theology*, 205. Adam is related to the entire human race as its covenant head, and therefore his sin meant that his descendants by ordinal generation were subject to death as the punishment due to his in. See Beeke and Jones, 206.

²¹⁶ McClure and Rollinson, *The Westminster Confession of Faith*, 13.

²¹⁷ John Bunyan, *Pilgrim's Progress*, 53.

²¹⁸ John Bunyan, *Pilgrim's Progress*, 8-9.

²¹⁹ Watson, *The Doctrine of Repentance*, 61.

²²⁰ The way to eternal life is narrow because it is through Jesus alone. Crossway Bibles, *The ESV Study Bible*, English Standard Version, (Wheaton, IL, 2008), 1834.

That said, there is no denying that the Wicket Gate represents Jesus Christ in the allegory. For Christians to start their journey to the Celestial City, they must enter through the Wicket Gate to fellowship with Jesus.²²¹ Similar to a door, on one side is where Christian came from (Figure 2), which is the City of Destruction; however, his past is behind him the City of Destruction,²²² and he walks on a path with his old life behind and with his new life in Christ.

Christian knocking at the gate

Fig 2. John Bunyan, *Pilgrim's Progress (Parts 1 & 2): Updated, Modern English. More Than 100 illustrations*, (Aneko Press. 2015, Apple Books), 27.

²²¹ As the Puritans taught, “mere agreement is not the same as personal trust. For in faith, we do not simply acknowledge the fact that Christ is Lord and Savior, we go to look to Him, go to Him, receive Him, rest on Him, surrender all to Him, submit to and depend on Him.” Beeke and Reeves, *Following God Fully*, 66.

²²² “Forsaking sin must be like forsaking one’s native soil, never more to return to it.” Watson, *The Doctrine of Repentance*, 61. “In true repentance, the heart points directly to God just as the compass needle points to the North Pole.” Watson, *The Doctrine of Repentance*, 61.

3. *Worldly Wiseman and Evangelist*

Christian meets two characters before reaching the Wicket Gate: a Worldly Wiseman and an Evangelist. In both characters, Bunyan demonstrates the importance of the Christian experience being rooted in sound biblical doctrine, and if it's not, one will be led astray. With that said, Christian was suffering from his burden of sin and his convictions, and he wanted to find the remedy to it. Initially, Evangelist found him and pointed to the wicket gate.²²³ However, he later encountered another character named Worldly Wisemen, who came from Carnal Policy,²²⁴ and said there was a faster way for Christian to remove his burdens through Legality.²²⁵ Similar to how it is essential to understand the fullness and origin of men, it is the same thing when it comes to understanding the work of God, including the convictions of sin in His righteousness, which is also essential to know alongside what is the divine solution to the problem of the soul. The path Wiseman suggested to Christian made it worse. Bunyan demonstrates that one cannot resolve one's sin issues through human efforts or the religion of lawkeeping.

4. *The Cross and Stone Tomb*

After Christian continues to walk further into his new pilgrimage, he encounters the cross and the stone tomb. As Christian approached the cross, his burden loosened, fell, and rolled into the tomb.²²⁶ In Bunyan's life, Bunyan struggled with the assurance of salvation. He did not receive his assurance until he meditated on Christ's righteousness in the field. Based on Bunyan's autobiography, Christian converted at the Wicket Gate but didn't receive assurance of his conversion until the cross. With that, he communicates that believers do not always have assurance right at conversion; it can take time.²²⁷ Solo Christo is highlighted through the divine

²²³ John Bunyan, *Pilgrim's Progress*, 8.

²²⁴ John Bunyan, *Pilgrim's Progress*, 17. Carnal is also described to be located close to the City of Destruction, with the implication of the cities before the Wicket representing humanity's dire state in Adam, carnal policy is a reference to human knowledge related to our physical bodies and mind, subtracting God's knowledge.

²²⁵ Legality represents the law, Worldly Wiseman has mentioned that he is judicial. Additionally, Evangelist's correction to Christian said the reason Worldly Wiseman's solution did not work is because of Galatians 3:10 which was referenced, that "those who trust in the works of the law are under the curse." John Bunyan, *Pilgrim's Progress*, 24.

²²⁶ John Bunyan, *Pilgrim's Progress*, 42.

²²⁷ The Puritans did believe that conversion was a process (that was def the case for John Bunyan. See Beeke and Jones, *A Puritan Theology*, 450.

supernatural work of death and resurrection. With a supernatural issue of sin, there is only a supernatural solution.²²⁸ In this case, the solution to humanity's sins and burdens is the cross of Christ because Jesus, as the Lamb of God, was the one who took the sins away.²²⁹ Christian's burden disappearing inside the tomb affirms Christ's resurrection as the new creation order.²³⁰

5. *The Three Shining Ones*

Shortly after his burden fell off, Christian was greeted by three shining ones who had reckoned to him the righteousness of Christ.²³¹ Following the release of a sinner's burden, the new creation order demonstrates the work of Jesus is an imputation.²³² Because of his death and resurrection, the righteousness of Christ reckons the sinner with the following:

- i. Forgiveness of sins²³³
- ii. New change of clothes from the old rags
- iii. Mark on Christian's forehead and a scroll with a seal²³⁴

The three things are essential because not only are Christians forgiven, but they are redeemed. The first shining one, telling him his sins are forgiven, demonstrates the sinner's justification before God with Christ's imputed righteousness. The old rags changed for new clothes depict the old nature before God was replaced with a new nature in Jesus.²³⁵ In addition, the mark on the

²²⁸ “The Reformers and their heirs, for example, viewed sin primarily as a violation of God's holy and righteous character. This focus entailed a proper sense of retributive justice tied to God's moral nature. Because sin offends God, and because God is holy and just, God must punish sin unless there is full satisfaction for it. But humanity cannot atone for its own sin given its divine object. Only Christ, God the Son incarnate, can stand in our place and act as our substitute by bearing our sin, paying the penalty for it, and removing its condemnation.” Wellum, *Christ Alone*, 173.

²²⁹ “The cross conveys the truth that the human race is in a pitiful state; it is a guilty, depraved, helpless sinner under the sentence of death.” Wellum, *Christ Alone*, 176. It also reminds of Jesus because “the cross work accomplished everything for us and in our place bears the penalty we deserve.” See Wellum, *Christ Alone*, 176.

²³⁰ Wellum, *Christ Alone*, 149.

²³¹ See Andy Draycott's article on exploring the different viewpoints on who the three shining ones are. Draycott, Andy. “Three Shining Ones at the Cross in the Pilgrim's Progress: Angels, Trinity, or Church?” *Journal of the Evangelical Theological Society* 66, no. 2 (June 2023): 323–41.

²³² “They are righteous because they belong to Jesus Christ, they are righteous because they are married to Christ. Schreiner, *Faith Alone*, 44.

²³³ The covering of propitiation is in reference to sin that is being covered and the covering of sin is cleansing and forgiveness and its before God that the covering takes place. See Murray, *Redemption Accomplished and Applied*, 26.

²³⁴ John Bunyan, *Pilgrim's Progress*, 43-44.

²³⁵ The pair of clothes is described as “Christ restoring us to true and substantial integrity.” See Calvin, *Institutes of the Christian Religion*, 107.

Christian's forehead is a symbolic depiction of adoption through the indwelling of the Holy Spirit,²³⁶ and how when God adopts people into His family, they are His, and no one snatches them out.²³⁷

6. Formalist and Hypocrisy

In the Puritans' days, the treatment of a reformed Church of England was a rollercoaster. Leaders like Henry VIII broke the ties with Roman Catholicism but never received Protestant worship.²³⁸ Mary Tudor also undid Edward VI's Protestant implementations and set all of England to Roman Catholicism.²³⁹ Characters Formalist and Hypocrisy's behaviors reflecting parliament's religiosity:

“You don't have to trouble yourself about that. Our manner of climbing over the wall is a well-established custom. In fact, many witnesses have testified that it is an accepted route which has been well established.”²⁴⁰

“Our tradition has been accepted for a long time – more than a thousand years. Without a doubt it will be admitted as a legal ordinance by any impartial judge. And from a practical standpoint, what difference does it make how we get on this way as long as we get onto it? If we are in, we are in. From what you've told us, you're in by way of the wicket gate and we by tumbling over the wall. So what makes your present condition any better than ours”²⁴¹

The clothes are justification in and for the sake of His only son, Jesus Christ. They enjoy the liberties and privileges of God's children.” See McClure and Rollinson, *The Westminster Confession of Faith*, 21. “He imputed to them the obedience and judicial satisfaction earned by Christ.” See McClure and Rollinson, *The Westminster Confession of Faith*, 19.

²³⁶ McClure and Rollinson, *The Westminster Confession of Faith*, 54.

²³⁷ “Adoption into the family of God is not from nature, but from our heavenly Father, benign sealed in the elect by the Spirit of regeneration.” See Calvin, *Institutes of the Christian Religion*, 1021.

²³⁸ Beeke and Reeves, *Following God Fully*, 7.

²³⁹ Beeke and Reeves, 7.

²⁴⁰ John Bunyan, *Pilgrim's Progress*, 46.

²⁴¹ John Bunyan, *Pilgrim's Progress*, 46.

Formalist and Hypocrisy coming into the way over the wall

Fig 3. John Bunyan, *Pilgrim's Progress (Parts 1 & 2): Updated, Modern English. More Than 100 illustrations*, (Aneko Press. 2015, Apple Books), 46.

Formalist and Hypocrisy not only represent the religious tendencies of Parliament and its conformists, but it's where Bunyan, in his text, seals the deal that that people who follow the claim they follow the Lord and His will but with their add-ons and traditions that they believe are on the same level as their methods lack the righteousness of Christ (Figure 3), they are forming their self-righteousness.²⁴² Formalist's name suggests an external religious identity,²⁴³ while

²⁴² "Vainglory is where all formalists and hypocrites come from. They glory in themselves. They think their own hearts are right. They conclude that their natural goodness suffices, and therefore a few forms and a bare profession will serve them in the day of judgment." See Spurgeon, *Pictures from Pilgrim's Progress*, 59-60.

²⁴³ "Oh! Say hey, "we will try to be Christians; and, in order to be Christians, there are such-and-such outward actions to be performed. We will attend the prayer-meeting; we will go to the Bible-classes; we will see the elders; we will be baptized; we will join the church; and when we have done all this, we shall have got into the right road certainly. Have we not received as it were, the certificate of God's own Church that we are all right? It is true that we have tumbled over the wall; we have not been humbled on accounts of sin; we have not put our trust in the Lord Jesus Christ; still, we are in the right way; does not everybody say that we are? Therefore, all must be well with us." Such was Formalst." See Spurgeon, 58.

Hypocrisy demonstrates a false notion of belief for self-gain.²⁴⁴ The life of the church of Christ begins by entering the wicket gate and not cheating oneself inside with anything but.²⁴⁵ Solo Christo and Sola Fide are highlighted in Bunyan's craft for Formalist and Hypocrisy, because one tends to say one is a Christian without ever entering Christ's fellowship.²⁴⁶

7. *Palace Beautiful*

Throughout the story, there are resting places for pilgrims on the journey to the Celestial City. They vary from shady spots to rivers and buildings. One of the first buildings the pilgrims encountered was Palace Beautiful. Several elements exist regarding Palace Beautiful's route, opposition, and purposes. In the story, Palace Beautiful follows after pilgrims continue through the narrow path upward toward and through Hill Difficulty.²⁴⁷ After the cross, the road has an intersection, with the straying yet easy paths labeled Danger and Destruction.²⁴⁸ Meanwhile, the hardest way -Hill Difficulty- continues straight on the path to the Celestial City. Trials are inevitable in the journey to Christ, but Christians are assured that God helps.²⁴⁹ Before climbing the hill, Christian drank from the spring to refresh himself.²⁵⁰ Like water providing endurance before a difficult walk, Christ is like a refreshing spring in a believer's life, which preserves and enables them to continue walking the Christian path. As Christian said, the way of life is hard, but it is better to go that way as it's the right way.²⁵¹

At the entrance of Palace Beautiful, two lions were in the way. The lions would scare away pilgrims from progressing, thinking they would devour them.²⁵² The two lions represent the opposition and testing of a pilgrim's faith.²⁵³ There are difficulties and opposition against

²⁴⁴ “But Hypocrisy said in his heart, “Ah! It is all a pretty story, but then it is a very respectable story, and if I pretend to believe it, people will think the better of me.” See Spurgeon, 58-59.

²⁴⁵ “It is a terrible proof of hypocrisy and formalism when you say to others, ‘Let each man keep to his own religion; you go your way, and leave me to mine; I daresay I am as right as you are.’” See Spurgeon, 62.

²⁴⁶ “How may a man be made right before God? We are justified by faith alone (sola fide), in Christ alone (solo Christo), the Protestant Reformers answered. Johnson, *The Case for Traditional Protestantism*, 75.

²⁴⁷ John Bunyan, *Pilgrim's Progress*, 47.

²⁴⁸ John Bunyan, *Pilgrim's Progress*, 48.

²⁴⁹ Spurgeon, *Pictures from Pilgrim's Progress*, 67.

²⁵⁰ John Bunyan, *Pilgrim's Progress*, 49.

²⁵¹ John Bunyan, *Pilgrim's Progress*, 49.

²⁵² John Bunyan, *Pilgrim's Progress*, 50-51.

²⁵³ “It is quite true that there are difficulties in the way of those who profess to be followers of the Lord Jesus Christ. We do not desire to conceal this fact, and we do not wish you to come amongst us without counting the cost.” See Spurgeon, *Pictures from Pilgrim's Progress*, 71.

identifying with a Christian church. In Bunyan's day, the lions of opposition were the Church of England and Monarchy opposing Nonconformists and their attempts at a reformed church. Due to the restoration of the monarchy, the Puritans were ejected from the church of England²⁵⁴ for not conforming to the state's policies. In addition, the state banned Nonconformists from conducting at home services.²⁵⁵ However, the Puritans -including Bunyan- disregarded the guidelines and held gatherings and teachings in barns.²⁵⁶ As for testing a pilgrim's faith, the lions at Palace Beautiful's entryway are chained and ultimately do not harm the church; instead, they test pilgrims and their faith.²⁵⁷ In moments of church opposition, and the Puritan's case, oppression, believers press on, knowing the lions have limited power and cannot dismantle Christ's church, for they are chained and under the control of the Lord God Almighty.²⁵⁸

As for its purposes, Palace Beautiful represents the fellowship and expertise of the Church of Christ. Before Christian enters Palace Beautiful, he meets Watchful, who oversees Palace Beautiful. Watchful asks Christian several questions about his pilgrimage, such as where he has come from.²⁵⁹ Watchful described Palace Beautiful as a place of pilgrims that was built by the Lord of the hill for the relief and security of pilgrims (Figure 4).²⁶⁰ Bunyan's reference to the hill is tied to Matthew 5:14, where Jesus said, "You are the light of the world. A city set on a hill cannot be hidden."²⁶¹ The Lord of the hill is Jesus, where Palace Beautiful has Christ as the cornerstone, and their profession of faith and practice of holiness is the foundation.²⁶² In practicing the profession and holiness, the church is made up of Christians who walked through the Wicket Gate and are walking in the light of Christ despite troubles, as Christian demonstrated when he told Watchful of his mistake of leaving his scroll at a place where he slept, had to go back, but pressed on the journey."²⁶³

²⁵⁴ Beeke and Peterson, *Meet the Puritans*, 8.

²⁵⁵ Beeke and Peterson, 8.

²⁵⁶ Johnson and Pastoor, *Historical Dictionary of the Puritans*, 86

²⁵⁷ John Bunyan, *Pilgrim's Progress*, 52.

²⁵⁸ Spurgeon, *Pictures from Pilgrim's Progress*, 71.

²⁵⁹ John Bunyan, *Pilgrim's Progress*, 53.

²⁶⁰ John Bunyan, *Pilgrim's Progress*, 53.

²⁶¹ ESV Study Bible, the context of the verse and the ones before and after it is saying that the disciples of Jesus have the light of the kingdom in them and it's a testimony that is illuminated on a hill for all to see." Crossway Bibles, *The ESV Study Bible, English Standard Version*, (Wheaton, IL, 2008), 1828.

²⁶² John Owen, *The True Nature of a Gospel Church*, 16.

²⁶³ John Bunyan, *Pilgrim's Progress*, 53.

Watchful also represents a minister who oversees outside buildings for pilgrims and helps them make entryway by disregarding and passing through the lions.²⁶⁴ In the church fellowship, there proceeds an examination of the pilgrim's story to see if they would benefit from the perks of the Palace, which was specifically built to entertain pilgrims,²⁶⁵ so was demonstrated with Discretion being summoned to talk to Christian and later calling more family members to greet and welcome him into the Palace.²⁶⁶ In the church, fellowship conversations centering the cross²⁶⁷ highlight their outward profession of Jesus as their Lord. The profession is also present in the teachings on core Christian doctrines, such as the Trinity, the Bible, atonement, and eternity.²⁶⁸ The remedy for spiritual wounds through the brethren reflects Christ. Their healings are with Jesus's blood, as the physician Dr Skill showed after healing Christiana's son Matthew from Beelzebub's orchard through Christ's flesh, blood, salt, and repentance.²⁶⁹ Since the church was purchased with the blood of Christ,²⁷⁰ through the same blood that they find healing during their pilgrimage. As Mr. Skill told Christiana, "it is a universal pill goof against all diseases pilgrims are confronted with and when it is well prepared, it will keep for time immemorial."²⁷¹

²⁶⁴ "Watchful means the good minister, who ought to be ever watchful for souls." See Spurgeon, Pictures from Pilgrim's Progress, 71.

²⁶⁵ John Bunyan, *Pilgrim's Progress*, 54.

²⁶⁶ "We shall also ask you what you are doing for Christ, and what you think of Christ, and what are your habits with regard to reading the Scriptures, and private prayer, and such things." See Spurgeon, Pictures from Pilgrim's Progress, 78.

²⁶⁷ John Bunyan, *Pilgrim's Progress*, 59-60.

²⁶⁸ John Bunyan, *Pilgrim's Progress*, 244-248.

²⁶⁹ John Bunyan, *Pilgrim's Progress*, 242.

²⁷⁰ Bannerman, *The Church of Christ*, 60.

²⁷¹ John Bunyan, *Pilgrim's Progress*, 243-244.

The welcome at the palace Beautiful

Fig 4. John Bunyan, *Pilgrim's Progress (Parts 1 & 2): Updated, Modern English. More Than 100 illustrations*, (Aneko Press. 2015, Apple Books), 234.

8. Mr. Great Heart

The key people in the church's spiritual health is the pastor's role, who preaches biblical doctrine. One of the allegories that Bunyan used to communicate a pastor's heart and devotion was through the Interpreter's visions that he showed Christian of a man clenching the Bible with his hand.²⁷² According to the Puritans, the pastor was committed to the eternal affairs of building up believers devoted to Christ and grounded in the Bible.²⁷³ The man in the Interpreter's vision also had a crown on his head, had the word behind him, and pleaded to men of the world.²⁷⁴ The Homeric phrase for "pastor" is "the shepherd of the people."²⁷⁵ With that, the pastor is a shepherd

²⁷² John Bunyan, *Pilgrim's Progress*, 31.

²⁷³ Beeke and Reeves, *Following God Fully*, 114.

²⁷⁴ John Bunyan, *Pilgrim's Progress*, 31.

²⁷⁵ Bannerman, *The Church of Christ*, 289.

with a divine appointment as an authority figure in the church of Christ.²⁷⁶ According to John Owen, the principal duty of a pastor is to feed the flock through diligently preaching the word.²⁷⁷ In preaching the word, the pastors are working diligently in the labor for the conversion of souls to Christ,²⁷⁸ as demonstrated with the man pleading to the men of the world.

Mr. Great Heart

Fig 5. John Bunyan, *Pilgrim's Progress (Parts 1 & 2): Updated, Modern English. More Than 100 illustrations*, (Aneko Press. 2015, Apple Books), 223.

With that said the pilgrims in part two had a spiritual guide up until reaching the Celestial City named Mr. Great Heart (Figure 5). Like the man in the Interpreter's vision, Mr. Great Heart clenched and preached the Bible to the pilgrims. When the pilgrims walked by the empty tomb,

²⁷⁶ Bannerman, *The Church of Christ*, 824.

²⁷⁷ John Owen, *The True Nature of a Gospel Church*, 154.

²⁷⁸ John Owen, *The True Nature of a Gospel Church*, 170.

Christiana asked Mr. Great Heart a question relating to the empty tomb²⁷⁹ with Great Heart answering her question with various verses from Scripture in the following pages.²⁸⁰ Great Heart set aside all other commitments,²⁸¹ and was devoted to guiding and preaching pilgrims to the Celestial City. As a pastor, Bunyan had a special love for Christians who were weak in faith²⁸² and paid more attention to the diversity in the life of faith²⁸³ in the allegory's second story. Throughout part two, weaker pilgrims are under the care and guidance of Mr. Great Heart, who are susceptible to spiritual vulnerabilities²⁸⁴ such as Feeble Mind and Mr. Despondency.

9. *Doubting Castle*

Throughout part two, Mr. Great Heart helps to encourage pilgrims to conquer spiritual barriers; one of those examples is Doubting Castle. In the allegory, the Doubting Castle, which Giant Despair ruled.²⁸⁵ Christian and Hopeful fell victim to Giant Despair because they slept on his grounds.²⁸⁶ When the pilgrims reached Doubting Castle and remembered the Christians' experience with it, Mr. Great asked who wanted to go with him to demolish the castle.²⁸⁷ With the help of Christiana's four sons and Old Honest (Figure 6), Doubting Castle was destroyed, and Giant Despair was killed by Great Heart.²⁸⁸ One of the roles of a pastor is to know the state of the flock, particularly their strengths, weaknesses, and spiritual decays and thrivings.²⁸⁹ In the story, Giant Despair aims to destroy God's pilgrims.²⁹⁰ With that, Doubting Castle posed a threat to the pilgrimage. However, Great Heart set an example for the pilgrims to defeat spiritual strongholds so the pilgrims could feel encouraged to do the same.²⁹¹

²⁷⁹ John Bunyan, *Pilgrim's Progress*, 223-225.

²⁸⁰ John Bunyan, *Pilgrim's Progress*, 223-225.

²⁸¹ John Owen, *The True Nature of a Gospel Church*, 155.

²⁸² John Bunyan had a special love for Christians who are weak in faith and assurance. De Vries, John Bunyan and His Relevance for Today, 68.

²⁸³ De Vries, 68.

²⁸⁴ Part two of *Pilgrim's Progress*, compared to the first part, had various characters who are vulnerable, because Bunyan grew an understanding of the vulnerability of the Christian on his pilgrimage. Geoff Thomas, John Bunyan: His Life, Writing, and Influence, 62.

²⁸⁵ John Bunyan, *Pilgrim's Progress*, 128-129.

²⁸⁶ John Bunyan, *Pilgrim's Progress*, 126-129.

²⁸⁷ John Bunyan, *Pilgrim's Progress*, 295.

²⁸⁸ *Pilgrim's Progress*, pg 295-297.

²⁸⁹ John Owen, *The True Nature of a Gospel Church*, 105.

²⁹⁰ *Pilgrim's Progress*, pg 295-297.

²⁹¹ Great heart said "Though that last claim cannot be true in every case, I do have a commandment to resist sin, to overcome evil, and to fight the good fight of faith. I have to ask, with whom should I fight

Great Heart and the sons of Christiana destroy Doubting Castle

Fig 6. John Bunyan, *Pilgrim's Progress (Parts 1 & 2): Updated, Modern English. More Than 100 illustrations*, (Aneko Press. 2015, Apple Books), 297.

10. *The Man with a Container of Oil*

One of the visions Christian was shown at the Interpreter's House was a fireplace at the wall. In the vision, a man stood by and was throwing water to diminish the fire. Despite the man's efforts, the fire continued to burn hotter.²⁹² The Interpreter then showed Christian behind the wall, and there was another man who was continuing to pour oil on the fire, which was the reason the fire stayed burning.²⁹³ The Interpreter explained to Christian that the man with the water is the devil, the fire is the work of "God's grace in the soul of man," and the man with the oil keeping the fire alive is Christ.²⁹⁴ The Interpreter's vision of Christianity demonstrates the

this good fight, if not with giant Despair? I will therefore attempt to take his life and to demolish Doubting Castle. Then he asked, "Who will go with me?." John Bunyan, *Pilgrim's Progress*, pg 295.

²⁹² *Pilgrim's Progress*, pg 34-35.

²⁹³ *Pilgrim's Progress*, pg 34-35.

²⁹⁴ *Pilgrim's Progress*, pg 34-35.

doctrine of perseverance. In the Westminster Confession of Faith, chapter 17 regarding the perseverance of the saints, it says that perseverance is based on the efficacy of the merit and intercession of Jesus Christ.²⁹⁵ It further indicates that once a believer is adopted into Christ through faith, Christ holds intercedes in satanic trials and opposition. An example of Christ's intercession in the text is Doubting Castle, where pilgrims were trapped in their spiritual doubts. Christian and Hopeful were in the deep dungeons in Doubting Castle. However, the key to unlocking the prison door was a key wrapped around Christ's chest called "Promise."²⁹⁶ To overcome spiritual doubt, it represents the promises of Christ, never casting away those who have trusted and believed in Him.²⁹⁷ Despite dark situations like Doubting Castle, the key to getting out of the doubt is remembering the promises and perseverance of God who had saved them on the cross and rose three days later according to the biblical accounts. Similar to the man keeping the fire alive with the oil, the promises and character of Christ keep a believer's faith alive amidst spiritual trials and doubt.

II. Mr Fearing

One of the pilgrims trusted to Mr. Great Heart was Mr. Fearing. The book described him as a Pilgrim who "understood the root of the matter but was one of the most troublesome pilgrims."²⁹⁸ Great Heart was his guide, starting at the Interpreter's house and going up to the gates of the Celestial City. Aside from Mr Great Heart's attitude toward Fearing being one of devotion, as demonstrated when he said, "I could bear it well enough. Men of my calling are often entrusted to conduct men like him."²⁹⁹ The men calling Great Heart referenced the pastors and church leadership who oversee the church's spiritual struggles. To understand the meaning of Fearing and his troublesome nature, an excellent place to start is to understand what or why made him so troublesome. For starters, Mr. Fearing came from the town of Stupidity, which is four degrees north of the City of Destruction,³⁰⁰ and was afraid of whether he would reach the place he desired to go (the Celestial City) and ended up in the slough of Despond for more than a

²⁹⁵ McClure and Rollinson, *The Westminster Confession of Faith*, 27.

²⁹⁶ *Pilgrim's Progress*, pg 133.

²⁹⁷ Believers drawing and being near to God is a work of Him drawing sinners, Crossway Bibles, The ESV Study Bible, English Standard Version, (Wheaton, IL, 2008), 2035.

²⁹⁸ John Bunyan, *Pilgrim's Progress*, 263.

²⁹⁹ John Bunyan, *Pilgrim's Progress*, 263.

³⁰⁰ John Bunyan, *Pilgrim's Progress*, 288.

month.³⁰¹ The text also wrote how Fearing was standing at the Wicket Gate watching other pilgrims pass through, and he stood there for a long time because he said he was not worthy and also afraid to knock on the gate that leads to a renewed life in Christ. After passing the gate and staying at the Interpreter's House, Mr. Fearing had no issue with all the obstacles that Christian and the pilgrims from part 2 encountered. Mr. Great Heart even found Mr. Fearing kissing the flowers at the Valley of Humiliation (Figure 7).

Mr. Fearing in the Valley of Humiliation

Fig 7. John Bunyan, *Pilgrim's Progress (Parts 1 & 2): Updated, Modern English. More Than 100 illustrations*, (Aneko Press. 2015, Apple Books), 266.

Mr. Great Heart concluded that Mr. Fearing and himself departed after Fearing had crossed the River of Death. Great Heart had no doubts about Mr. Fearing and concluded that he had good attributes as a pilgrim, and Honest followed up by saying that Mr. Fearing was zealous

³⁰¹ John Bunyan, *Pilgrim's Progress*, 264.

and did not fear difficulties. Instead, it was only sin, death, and hell that filled him with terror because he had some doubts about his share in that Celestial country³⁰² Mr Great Heart also concluded that all of the things that troubled him were from the weakness of his mind.³⁰³ As demonstrated through the Great Heart's recounting of Fearing's pilgrimage, Fearing obtained his name because he fears being left out of God's promises of eternal life. Through his timidity at the Wicket Gate and his reaction to arriving at the River of Death, there was a fear of not reaching Heaven.

“Upon the Enchanted Ground, he was very alert and wakeful, but when he reached the river and realized there was no bridge, he again became dejected. ‘Now, now,’ he said, ‘I will be drowned forever and never see the comfort of the face I have come so many miles to behold’³⁰⁴

Every Christian will face fears or have fears. The Christian walk is only sometimes heroic, and it could be better. However, as the reformers and Puritans have taught, our Christian walk is not based on our performance to be good, because if that was the case, then our salvation is based on performance or being 'good' and as Bunyan demonstrated at the Wicket Gate through Formalist and Hypocrisy, our salvation in Christ is only merited through His work. He is the one doing the work. He started in every church member alive, as demonstrated by the man with the oil. That said, spiritual weaknesses and vulnerabilities in the church are a reality in a congregation. Even after a believer in Christ has been made new through divine transformation, there are still doubts because while believers are still on earth, there is human nature to deal with, and part of that humanity's nature is emotions such as fear.

The realities of spiritual weakness are demonstrated in the following pages, which are the pilgrims' thoughts about the testimony of Mr. Fearing. Here are the following statements on the Pilgrims regarding Fearing's story:

³⁰² John Bunyan, *Pilgrim's Progress*, 268.

³⁰³ John Bunyan, *Pilgrim's Progress*, 268.

³⁰⁴ John Bunyan, *Pilgrim's Progress*, 267.

“Then Christiana said, ‘Hearing about Mr. Fearing and his struggles has done me good, because I thought nobody else was like me. But now I see a similarity between this good man and me’”³⁰⁵

“Mercy said, ‘I’d also like to speak my heart if you’ll permit me. For I must say, I too am similar to him in another way. For I have always been more afraid of the lake and the loss of a place in paradise than I have been about the loss of other things’”³⁰⁶

“Matthew said, I experienced fear too, but for me it was a fear that perhaps I wasn’t saved - that I lacked within me the thing that accompanies salvation. But now that I know how it was for Mr. Fearing that he arrived at the Celestial City and gained admittance, why wouldn’t it go well with me too?”³⁰⁷

With that said, spiritual weakness is a reality because even though other Christians may not have the exact struggle, there are overlaps to the struggles. After all, the Christian journey is not one of solitude but of fellowship with other Christians who also have their share of struggles. However, every believer is encouraged by the others' struggles because they are relatable, as all believers in Christ are on the same journey to Him in Heaven. The diversity of spiritual weakness in the church further amplifies the unity of the church because the church can be reassured with previous and current Christian struggles because they can be sure they are on the right track and that their brothers and sisters in the faith and church leaders and there for them amidst the trials.

12. Gaius Inn

During the pilgrimage journey in part two, Christiana expressed her wishes for an inn to refresh herself and her children because they were weary of the pilgrimage.³⁰⁸ One of the older pilgrims, Mr. Honest, suggested an inn where a disciple named Gaius runs.³⁰⁹ Like Palace

³⁰⁵ John Bunyan, *Pilgrim’s Progress*, 268.

³⁰⁶ John Bunyan, *Pilgrim’s Progress*, 269.

³⁰⁷ John Bunyan, *Pilgrim’s Progress*, 269.

³⁰⁸ John Bunyan, *Pilgrim’s Progress*, 272-274.

³⁰⁹ John Bunyan, *Pilgrim’s Progress*, 272-274.

Beautiful, Gaius Inn is another example of the church congregation's involvement in Christians' lifelong journey in Christ. One textual example demonstrates that Gaius Inn is a place of spiritual restoration for pilgrims as Gaius tells the pilgrims, "If you are true believers, for my house is only for pilgrims."³¹⁰

13. Mr Feeble Mind

During the pilgrim's stay at Gaius Inn, they searched and hunted Slay-Good, who was described as "annoys those traveling the King's highway."³¹¹ One of the Pilgrims that the group successfully captured back and welcomed to the inn after defeating Slay-good is Feeble Mind. Feeble-mind came from the town of Uncertainty.³¹² When the group of pilgrims prepares to leave Gaius Inn, Feeble-Minded is reluctant because he feels insecure that the group of pilgrims is robust and calls himself weak; he considers himself a man of many infirmities and thinks that stronger believers bear to make him uncomfortable.³¹³ Characters such as Feeble Mind demonstrate that there are believers who are not great company, but the church should not exclude them, for they are the people who need church fellowship as encouragement.³¹⁴ However, Mr. Great Heart insists that Feeble Minded goes along with them because Great Heart is commissioned to comfort the feeble-minded to be their strong protector,³¹⁵ and he promises to help him and not leave them behind.³¹⁶

14. The Land of Beulah

Close to the end of the pilgrimage, the pilgrims arrive to another place where weary pilgrims go and rest:³¹⁷ the land of Beulah. Pilgrims were described as using anything in the land since they belonged more to the country than any other.³¹⁸ In addition, the Master sends his messengers to the land, telling pilgrims that He is waiting for them in the Celestial City.

³¹⁰ John Bunyan, *Pilgrim's Progress*, 272-274.

³¹¹ John Bunyan, *Pilgrim's Progress*, 67.

³¹² John Bunyan, *Pilgrim's Progress*, 67.

³¹³ John Bunyan, *Pilgrim's Progress*, 285.

³¹⁴ Spurgeon, *Pictures from Pilgrim's Progress*, 136.

³¹⁵ Spurgeon, *Pictures from Pilgrim's Progress*, 136.

³¹⁶ John Bunyan, *Pilgrim's Progress*, 285.

³¹⁷ John Bunyan, *Pilgrim's Progress*, 318.

³¹⁸ John Bunyan, *Pilgrim's Progress*, 318.

Allegorically, The land of Beulah is a place where pilgrims have complete faith,³¹⁹ and it was borderline between death and the Celestial City. Additionally, death is not a sorrowful subject³²⁰ in the land, because they had reached home to the Celestial.³²¹ One of the things the Puritans taught with justification was the imparting of Christ's life and perfect righteousness.³²² The pilgrim's allowance to use many items is a foretaste of the final step in salvation, according to the Puritans, glorification. As worded in Westminster, glorification is when believers receive the fullness of joy and refreshment that comes from the presence of Jesus³²³ because of the imparting of His life to a believer for eternity.

In the story, the pilgrims must cross the river of death to receive full joy. Mr. Feeble Mind was one of the pilgrims who was called to cross the river of death. Mr. Feeble mind had mentioned that his feeble mind would leave him behind.³²⁴ Like Mr. Despondency's message from the messenger of shouting for joy for his deliverance from his doubts, Mr. Feeble mind's struggles would pass the moment when he reached heaven.³²⁵ Despite a Christian's weaknesses due to the coals satan threw at their fire, the man in the oil was sustaining them up until the moment it was time for them to cross the river of death. As the Puritans taught, in salvation believers are preserved as they are sealed to the day of redemption.³²⁶

Discussion

The background and textual evidence demonstrate an intercorrelation between both topics, with Bunyan expounding critical themes in Christian doctrine, such as salvation and the church. In a similar connotation to the Reformers and Puritans, explaining the church without first talking about salvation is impossible. Like the necessity of Solus Christus being the lens of interpreting scripture and the practice of saving faith, the church must be regarded through salvation's atonement and newness. After all, her corporate fellowship and pastoral counseling are products of salvific results. Part of the restoration in salvation is walking in light of Christ's

³¹⁹ Spurgeon, *Pictures from Pilgrim's Progress*, 146.

³²⁰ Spurgeon, 145.

³²¹ Spurgeon, 146.

³²² Beeke and Reeves, *Following God Fully*, 69.

³²³ McClure and Rollinson, *The Westminster Confession of Faith*, 53.

³²⁴ John Bunyan, *Pilgrim's Progress*, 322.

³²⁵ John Bunyan, *Pilgrim's Progress*, 322.

³²⁶ McClure and Rollinson, *The Westminster Confession of Faith*, 27.

work, which was Him dying in her place. After all, Christian did not walk in the light of Christ until after the Wicket Gate, similar to Christiana in part two.

Part of the restoration process for the church includes the process of salvation. Understanding the process of salvation requires a doctrinal basis of who man is, who God is, what God did, and the need for God's solution. With allegories such as the Wicket Gate and the cross and tomb, Bunyan demonstrates the start of a new life and a divine institution as the corporate identity of each sinner reconciled to God. The heart of Bunyan's allegory of the Christian lifestyle, written in a time of religious persecution, is doctrine. Doctrinal reform was at the heart of Puritanism concerning Christianity's source of truth. Was the source what the state declared or what God declared six millennia ago?

As demonstrated through the characters of Formalist and Hypocrisy, it is easy to disregard literal biblical interpretation in favor of tradition or personal validation. Like any book, the Bible has a message with direction, and it is a reflection of God's character. If God calls Himself unchanging, how much more will His communication in the scriptures be ageless? As a contemporary example, Presbyterian Theologian J Gresham Machen said that Christianity was not based on feelings, but it was founded on a message based on doctrine.³²⁷

1. Christianity and Liberalism

Earlier in the paper, Liberalism has been briefly explained as a contemporary doctrinal teaching, emphasizing God using other means to forgive. Similar to the Puritans with Rome's influence on the church of England, J. Gresham Machen, in his book *Christianity and Liberalism*, laid out the doctrinal differences between Christianity and Liberalism in 1923. Through core doctrines such as God, sin, scripture, salvation, and the church, Liberalism was a different religion rather than a sect of Protestant Christianity.

After careful analysis, Machen defended similar topics to those the Puritans defended regarding the tenets of Christianity, such as scripture, salvation, and the church. Scripture, according to liberalism, was “human imaginings”³²⁸ and “aspirations about spiritual matters”³²⁹ instead of being inspired by God as declared in the Westminster Confession. Salvation was no

³²⁷ Machen, *Christianity and Liberalism*, 19.

³²⁸ Joshua D. Chatraw, Benjamin K. Forrest, and Alister E. McGrath, *The History of Apologetics: A Biographical and Methodological Introduction*, (Zondervan Academic, 2020), 469.

³²⁹ Chatraw, Forrest, and McGrath, *The History of Apologetic*, 469.

longer about how Jesus worked but about human efforts and following Jesus' example.³³⁰ Both Machen and the Puritans had a common denominator in their battles regarding salvation: its human effort. With the Puritans, preaching on regeneration was tedious due to Rome's influence of regeneration by physical water,³³¹ rather than the Spirit. With Machen, salvation was holding fast to a 'Christian-esque experience'³³² even if it contradicts the narrative of events in biblical accounts. In the Christian view, without the narrative event, the world is dark and humanity is lost in guilt of sin.³³³

With faulty and inconsistent doctrine, everything falls out of place. In relating to the correlation between salvation and the church, Machen highlighted Liberalism as having a poor salvific foundation regarding the church congregation. For starters, the cross of Christ is a crucial point in the redeemed lives of church members, and claiming to believe yet belittle it is absurd.³³⁴ Similar to the Puritans defending scriptural truths through creeds, a creed based on biblical principles helps maintain its identity in a consistent foundation. With a basis of the Solas of the Reformation, there is an established creed in the church. Even with missing points regarding salvation, such as a lack of reverence for the cross, as Machen witnessed, the church loses fundamental ground and steps at risk in a relative view.

i. Continuous Biblical Reform

With all said, a reformed church and individual life were necessary for the Puritans. Christian topics such as scripture, Christ, the church, and salvation mattered to the Puritans and Machen. With all the evidence about the relevancy of Bunyan's allegory, perhaps the trends of biblical proclamation call for a need for continuous biblical reform to be reminded of essential truths that built Christianity. Bunyan's allegory is only timeless and relevant because of his imagery rooted in unchanging doctrine, and that unchanging doctrine has been vital to reforming moments throughout church history. As demonstrated in Machen's battles, a doctrinal view shapes everything else. Because Bunyan shaped his allegory according to biblical truths

³³⁰ Chatraw, Forrest, and McGrath, *The History of Apologetics*, 469.

³³¹ Beeke, *Following God Fully*, 63.

³³² Machen, *Christianity and Liberalism*, 69

³³³ Machen, 69

³³⁴ Machen, 158

defended by the Reformers,³³⁵ the church's identity has roots in historical doctrine rather than contemporary experience. Because of Bunyan's faithful approach, the truths of restoration and walking in them have been and will continue to encourage bible believing Christians.

Conclusion

At the beginning of the paper, I asked the following two questions:

1. Why did Bunyan expound biblical truths of the Christian journey in allegorical writing?
2. What are the doctrinal implications of Bunyan's message to the audience, the church of Christ?

With the Puritan spirit of reforming the lives of people and the church, a relative view to salvation and the church is room for error. Similar to how the bible must be taken in an oriental context in the mindframe of Sola Scriptura, which will limit misinterpretations, the integrity of the allegory is destroyed when one is not considering its context. Bunyan wrote the allegory to demonstrate biblical truths to the ordinary person, and having a biblical understanding of core Christian doctrine will enrich the reader's view of the Christian faith and the church. The allegories of the previous towns, from the pilgrim's origin to the wicket gate and the cross and grave, create a basis for when Christian life starts. Christianity is not Christianity without Christ. Sadly, forms of Christianity have developed in the last century that have subtracted Christ from the conclusion. Once Christ is subtracted, there is no Christianity but no church of Christ, for the church depends on Christ as her groom. The church is not the church without Christ!

In reformer style, the Puritans were devoted to getting off the heart of the matter with the human soul. The heart of the reformation was to get to the root of the matter, Christ, and not let traditions or preconceptions diminish his glory. Similar to Machen's goal and the second question, a call to contemporary biblical reform is to be considered, particularly with the relationship of the church and the doctrines of Christian salvation. The Puritans sought that, and pilgrims brought to the matter in the allegory. As a foreword in Bunyan's autobiography wrote, "*The Pilgrim's Progress*, which he wrote in prison, has been and now is a guide to Christian

³³⁵ Although the paper highlights seventeenth-century English Puritanism and demonstrates its roots in the Protestant Reformation by briefly surveying its doctrinal standards. The paper's limitation is the historical survey and development of the doctrinal tenets that surfaced during the Reformation through examining previous church fathers and theologians.

pilgrims of all nations, kindreds, tribes, and people. It teaches them not to rest content in any national religion, but to personally search the Scripture earnestly supplicate to the God of mercy and truth that they may be guided to Christ as the Alpha and Omega.”³³⁶

³³⁶ John Bunyan, *Grace Abounding to the Chief of Sinners*, 29.

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